

Consequences Inference Method with Construction the Scheme from New Facts in Case of an Incomplete Knowledge Base in Predicate Calculus (Examples)

Simonov A.I.

Federal Government Budget Educational Institution of Higher Education "Vyatka State University",
Kirov, e-mail: asimonov215@gmail.com

The paper presents solutions of two problems using the method of logical inference of the consequences with the construction of an output scheme for an incompletely defined knowledge base in the predicate calculus.

Keywords: *consequences inference, scheme of logical inference, first-order predicate calculus, abductive consequences, incomplete knowledge base, additional facts, division of clauses.*

Вывод следствий с построением схемы вывода из новых фактов при не полностью определенной базе знаний в исчислении предикатов (примеры)

Симонов А.И.

ФГБОУ ВО «Вятский государственный университет», Киров, e-mail: asimonov215@gmail.com

В работе представлены решения двух задач с использованием метода логического вывода следствий с построением схемы вывода при не полностью определенной базе знаний в исчислении предикатов.

Ключевые слова: *вывод следствий, схема логического вывода, исчисление предикатов первого порядка, абдуктивные следствия, не полностью определенная база знаний, дополнительные факты, деление дизъюнктов.*

Описание параллельного выполнения ω -процедур в методе осуществляется с помощью специальной индексной функции, обеспечивающей уникальную идентификацию каждой процедуры и ее параметров. Введем индексную функцию $i(h)$ для индекса размером h , которую определим для индексной переменной t индуктивно следующим образом: $i(1) = t$, $t = 1, \dots, T$; $i(2) = i(1).t_{i(1)}$, $t_{i(1)} = 1, \dots, T_{i(1)}$ ($t.t = (1.t_1 | t_1 = 1, \dots, T_1)$, $(2.t_2 | t_2 = 1, \dots, T_2)$, $\dots$, $(T.t_T | t_T = 1, \dots, T_T)$); $i(3) = t.t.t_E$ ($E = t.t$), $i(3) = i(2).t_{i(2)}$, $t_{i(2)} = 1, \dots, T_{i(2)}$; и т.д. В общем случае $i(h) = i(h-1).t_{i(h-1)}$, $t_{i(h-1)} = 1, \dots, T_{i(h-1)}$. Будем считать, что $i(0)$ означает отсутствие индекса у индексруемой переменной, например, $T_{i(0)} = T$, а также, что $i(1) = i(0).t_{i(0)} = t$.

Индексная функция $i(h)$ задает индекс, который (при $h > 1$) состоит из константы, формируемой на основе значения функции $i(h - 1)$, и соответствующей этой константе переменной $t_{i(h-1)}$. Множество индексов, описываемых с помощью функции $i(h)$, формируется на основе значений функции $i(h - 1)$ и соответствующих им значений переменных $t_{i(h-1)} = 1, \dots, T_{i(h-1)}$. Например, при $T = T_1 = 3, T_2 = 2$ получим $i(1) = t, t = 1, 2, 3; i(2) = (1.t_1 | t_1 = 1, 2, 3), (2.t_2 | t_2 = 1, 2)$, то есть $i(2) = 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.1, 2.2$.

Задача о родственных связях

Применение метода вывода следствий с построением схемы вывода рассмотрим на примере о родственных связях, представленном в работе [Чери С. Логическое программирование и базы данных / С. Чери, Г. Готлоб, Л. Танка; пер. под ред. Л.А. Калиниченко. – М.: Мир, 1992. – 352 с.]. Исходными данными являются следующие предложения.

Отец (F) – это персона (Per) мужского пола (m), являющаяся родителем (P). Дед (GF) – это отец родителя. Родные братья или сестры (S) – это две различных (N) персоны, которые имеют общего родителя. Тетя (A) – это персона, которая приходится родной сестрой родителю. Известно, что Владимир (c) является родителем Натальи (d), и Виктория (b) – женщина (f). Новыми фактами является то, что Владимир – ребенок Дмитрия (a), и Владимир и Виктория – разные люди.

Формальная постановка задачи выглядит следующим образом.

- 1) $Per(x, m) \& P(x, y) \rightarrow F(x, y);$
- 2) $F(x, z) \& P(z, y) \rightarrow GF(x, y);$
- 3) $P(z, x) \& P(z, y) \& N(x, y) \rightarrow S(x, y);$
- 4) $Per(x, f) \& P(z, y) \& S(x, z) \rightarrow A(x, y);$
- 5) $1 \rightarrow P(c, d);$
- 6) $1 \rightarrow Per(b, f);$

Новые факты:

- 7) $1 \rightarrow P(a, c);$
- 8) $1 \rightarrow N(b, c).$

Преобразуем посылки и новые факты в дизъюнкты.

$$F_1 = P(c, d)[u, +];$$

$$F_2 = Per(b, f)[u, +];$$

$$D_1 = F(x, y)[1, +] \vee Per(x, m)[+, 1] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1], D'_1 = \langle Per(x, m)[+, 1] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1], F(x, y)[1, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_2 = GF(x, y)[2, +] \vee F(x, z)[+, 2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2], D'_2 = \langle F(x, z)[+, 2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2], GF(x, y)[2, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_3 = S(x, y)[3, +] \vee P(z, x)[+, 3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3],$$

$$D'_3 = \langle P(z, x)[+, 3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3], S(x, y)[3, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_4 = A(x, y)[4, +] \vee Per(x, f)[+, 4] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4],$$

$$D'_4 = \langle Per(x, f)[+, 4] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4], A(x, y)[4, +], \theta \rangle.$$

Новые факты:

$$N_1 = P(a, c)[n, +];$$

$$N_2 = N(b, c)[n, +].$$

Логический вывод будет состоять из следующих шагов.

1.1. **Определяются начальные значения.** $h = 1$, $M^D = \{D'_1, D'_2, D'_3, D'_4\}$, $M^N = \{N_1, N_2\} = \{P(a, c)[n, +], N(b, c)[n, +]\}$, $H = \gamma = 3$, $n_{max} = \delta = 2$, $R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$. Определяются начальные множества: $e_0 = M^F \bar{\cap} M^N = \emptyset$, $s^0 = \{e_0\}$, $c_1 = e_0$, $\pi^0 = \emptyset$, $c'_1 = \emptyset$, $\varphi^0 = \emptyset$, $g_1 = \emptyset$, $\eta^0 = \emptyset$, $u_1 = M^F = \{P(c, d)[u, +], Per(b, f)[u, +]\}$.

1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\psi_1 = \langle M^D, R_1, u_1, o_1, p_1, R_2, f_1, z_1, \delta \rangle$.

1.2.1.1. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_1 = \langle D'_1, R_1, u_1, Q_1, S_1, X_1, Y_1 \rangle$.

$$D'_1 = \langle Per(x, m)[+, 1_1] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1_1], F(x, y)[1_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +].$$

1.2.1.1.1. **Выполняется процедура** $\omega = \langle D'_1, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_1, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$Per(x, m)[+, 1_1]$	$P(x, y)[+, 1_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1	Δ_{12}
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{12} = \{a/x, c/y\}$, $\Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle$, $a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1]\}$, $b'_{12} = \langle b^{a_{12}}, b^{c_{12}}, \beta_{12} \rangle$, $b^{a_{12}} = Per(a, m)[+, 1_1]$, $\beta_{12} = \lambda_{12} = \{a/x, c/y\}$, $b^{c_{12}} = \beta_{12}D^c_1 = F(a, c)[1_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1$, $w_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$, $d^*_1 = 0$. Принимается $q = 2$.

$$x = a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = 0$, $d_1 = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$.

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

1.2.1.1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset$, $x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/x, c/y\}$	$Per(a, m)[+, 1_1]$
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	1

$$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = S_0.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = X_0.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

1.2.1.1.3. $Y = \{y_1\}, y_1 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1]$.

Поскольку $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0, X = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1]\}$.

1.2.1.1.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_1 = Q, S_1 = S, X_1 = X, Y_1 = Y$.

1.2.1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_2 = \langle D'_2, R_1, u_1, Q_2, S_2, X_2, Y_2 \rangle$.

$D'_2 = \langle F(x, z)[+, 2_1] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2_1], GF(x, y)[2_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$.

1.2.1.2.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_2, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_2, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$F(x, z)[+, 2_1]$	$P(z, y)[+, 2_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1	Δ_{12}
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}, \Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle, a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}2_1]\}, b'_{12} = \langle b^a_{12}, b^c_{12}, \beta_{12} \rangle,$

$b^a_{12} = F(x, a)[+, 2_1], \beta_{12} = \lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}, b^c_{12} = \beta_{12}D^c_2 = GF(x, c)[2_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1, w_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +], d^*_1 = 0$. Принимается $q = 2$.

$x = a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}2_1]\}$.

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = 0, d_1 = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$.

$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x$.

1.2.1.2.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/y\}$	$F(x, a)[+, 2_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1

$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}$.

$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = S_0$.

$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = X_0$.

$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1$.

1.2.1.2.3. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

1.2.1.2.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_2 = Q, S_2 = S, X_2 = X, Y_2 = Y$.

1.2.1.3. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_3 = \langle D'_3, R_1, u_1, Q_3, S_3, X_3, Y_3 \rangle$.

$D'_3 = \langle P(z, x)[+, 3_1] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3_1] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3_1], S(x, y)[3_1, +], \theta \rangle$, $R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$.

1.2.1.3.1. **Выполняется процедура** $\omega = \langle D'_3, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_3, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$P(z, x)[+, 3_1]$	$P(z, y)[+, 3_1]$	$N(x, y)[+, 3_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}	Δ_{12}	1
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}

$\lambda_{11} = \{a/z, c/x\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^{a_{11}}, b^{c_{11}}, \beta_{11} \rangle$,

$b^{a_{11}} = P(a, y)[+, 3_1] \vee N(c, y)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{a/z, c/x\}$, $b^{c_{11}} = \beta_{11}D^c_3 = S(c, y)[3_1, +]$.

$\lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}$, $\Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle$, $a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{12} = \langle b^{a_{12}}, b^{c_{12}}, \beta_{12} \rangle$,

$b^{a_{12}} = P(a, x)[+, 3_1] \vee N(x, c)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{12} = \lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}$, $b^{c_{12}} = \beta_{12}D^c_3 = S(x, c)[3_1, +]$.

$\lambda_{23} = \{b/x, c/y\}$, $\Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle$, $a_{23} = \{N(b, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{23} = \langle b^{a_{23}}, b^{c_{23}}, \beta_{23} \rangle$,

$b^{a_{23}} = P(z, b)[+, 3_1] \vee P(z, c)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{b/x, c/y\}$, $b^{c_{23}} = \beta_{23}D^c_3 = S(b, c)[3_1, +]$.

Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle\}$,

$d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1$, $w_1 = 0$, $d^*_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$,

$d^*_2 = R_1 \div w_2$, $w_2 = 0$, $d^*_2 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$,

$d^*_3 = R_1 \div w_3$, $w_3 = N(b, c)[n, +]$, $d^*_3 = P(a, c)[n, +]$.

$x = a_{11} \cup a_{12} \cup a_{23} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y\}3_1]\}$.

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle\}$,

$d^*_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$, $d_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$,

$d^*_2 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$, $d_2 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$,

$d^*_3 = P(a, c)[n, +]$, $d_3 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$.

$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d_3 \rangle\}$, $h = 0$, $S_0 = s$, $X_0 = x$.

1.2.1.3.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset$, $x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/x\}$	$P(a, y)[+, 3_1]$	$N(c, y)[+, 3_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}	1
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	1
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1	1
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{11} = \{c/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^{a_{11}}, b^{c_{11}}, \beta_{11} \rangle$,
 $b^{a_{11}} = N(c, c)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{11} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{11} = \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}$, $b^{c_{11}} = \beta_{11}b^{c_1} = S(c, c)[3_1, +]$. Принимается $q_1 = 0$.
 $s_1 = \emptyset$.

$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\}$, $d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}$, $w_{1.1} = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$,
 $d_{1.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_1 = 2$.

$x_1 = a_{11} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}3_1]\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_2 = \langle b'_2, d_2, q_2, n_2, s_2, x_2 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_2, d_2]$ и устанавливается $s_2 = \emptyset$, $x_2 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/y\}$	$P(a, x)[+, 3_1]$	$N(x, c)[+, 3_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}	1
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	Δ_{22}
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1	1
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{11} = \{c/x\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^{a_{11}}, b^{c_{11}}, \beta_{11} \rangle$,
 $b^{a_{11}} = N(c, c)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{11} = \beta_2 \cup \lambda_{11} = \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}$, $b^{c_{11}} = \beta_{11}b^{c_2} = S(c, c)[3_1, +]$.

$\lambda_{22} = \{b/x\}$, $\Delta_{22} = \langle a_{22}, b'_{22} \rangle$, $a_{22} = \{N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}$, $b'_{22} = \langle b^{a_{22}}, b^{c_{22}}, \beta_{22} \rangle$,
 $b^{a_{22}} = P(a, b)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{22} = \beta_2 \cup \lambda_{22} = \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}$, $b^{c_{22}} = \beta_{22}b^{c_2} = S(b, c)[3_1, +]$.

Принимается $q_2 = 0$.

$s_2 = \emptyset$.

$n_2 = \{\langle b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{2.2}, d_{2.2} \rangle\}$,

$d_{2.1} = d_2 \div w_{2.1}$, $w_{2.1} = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$, $d_{2.1} = N(b, c)[n, +]$,

$d_{2.2} = d_2 \div w_{2.2}$, $w_{2.2} = N(b, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$, $d_{2.2} = P(a, c)[n, +]$.

$x_2 = a_{11} \cup a_{22} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_3 = \langle b'_3, d_3, q_3, n_3, s_3, x_3 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_3, d_3]$ и устанавливается $s_3 = \emptyset$, $x_3 = \emptyset$.

$\{b/x, c/y\}$	$P(z, b)[+, 3_1]$	$P(z, c)[+, 3_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1	Δ_{12}
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1	1
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	1	1

$$\lambda_{12} = \{a/z\}, \quad \Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle, \quad a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1]\}, \quad b'_{12} = \langle b^a_{12}, b^c_{12}, \beta_{12} \rangle,$$

$b^a_{12} = P(a, b)[+, 3_1]$, $\beta_{12} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{12} = \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}$, $b^c_{12} = \beta_{12} b^c_3 = S(b, c)[3_1, +]$. Принимается $q_3 = 0$.

$$s_3 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_3 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle\},$$

$d_{3.1} = d_3 \div w_{3.1}$, $w_{3.1} = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$, $d_{3.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_3 = 2$.

$$x_3 = a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1]\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 \cup s_2 \cup s_3 = S_0.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 \cup x_2 \cup x_3 = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y\}3_1],$$

$P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1]\}.$

$$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{2.2}, d_{2.2} \rangle\}, h = 1.$$

1.2.1.3.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{2.1} = \langle b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1}, q_{2.1}, n_{2.1}, s_{2.1}, x_{2.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{2.1} = \emptyset$, $x_{2.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/y, c/x\}$	$N(c, c)[+, 3_1]$
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1

$$q_{2.1} = 1, n_{2.1} = \{\langle b'_{2.1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{2.1.1} = b'_{2.1}\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{2.2} = \langle b'_{2.2}, d_{2.2}, q_{2.2}, n_{2.2}, s_{2.2}, x_{2.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{2.2}, d_{2.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{2.2} = \emptyset$, $x_{2.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}$	$P(a, b)[+, 3_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1

$$q_{2.2} = 1, n_{2.2} = \{\langle b'_{2.2.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{2.2.1} = b'_{2.2}\}.$$

$$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{2.1} \cup s_{2.2} = S_1.$$

$$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{2.1} \cup x_{2.2} = X_1.$$

$$n'_2 = \emptyset, S = S_2, X = X_2.$$

1.2.1.3.4. $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}$,

$$y_1 = S(c, c)[\{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1, +] \vee N(c, c)[+, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1],$$

$$y_2 = S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +] \vee P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1].$$

Поскольку $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0$, $X = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], N(c, c)[+, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}$.

1.2.1.3.5. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_3 = Q$, $S_3 = S$, $X_3 = X$, $Y_3 = Y$.

1.2.1.4. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_4 = \langle D'_4, R_1, u_1, Q_4, S_4, X_4, Y_4 \rangle$.

$D'_4 = \langle Per(x, f)[+, 4_1] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4_1] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4_1], A(x, y)[4_1, +], \theta \rangle$, $R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$.

1.2.1.4.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_4, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_4, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$Per(x, f)[+, 4_1]$	$P(z, y)[+, 4_1]$	$S(x, z)[+, 4_1]$
$P(a, c)[n, +]$	1	Δ_{12}	1
$N(b, c)[n, +]$	1	1	1

$\lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}$, $\Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle$, $a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}4_1]\}$, $b'_{12} = \langle b^{a_{12}}, b^{c_{12}}, \beta_{12} \rangle$,
 $b^{a_{12}} = Per(x, f)[+, 4_1] \vee S(x, a)[+, 4_1]$, $\beta_{12} = \lambda_{12} = \{a/z, c/y\}$, $b^{c_{12}} = \beta_{12} D^c_4 = A(x, c)[4_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$,

$d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1$, $w_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +]$, $d^*_1 = 0$. Принимается $q = 2$.

$x = a_{12} = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}4_1]\}$.

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$,

$d^*_1 = 0$, $d_1 = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$,

$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}$, $h = 0$, $S_0 = s$, $X_0 = x$.

1.2.1.4.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset$, $x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/z, c/y\}$	$Per(x, f)[+, 4_1]$	$S(x, a)[+, 4_1]$
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1	1
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	Δ_{21}	1

$\lambda_{21} = \{b/x\}$, $\Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle$, $a_{21} = \{Per(b, f)[u, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1]\}$, $b'_{21} = \langle b^{a_{21}}, b^{c_{21}}, \beta_{21} \rangle$,
 $b^{a_{21}} = S(b, a)[+, 4_1]$, $\beta_{21} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{21} = \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}$, $b^{c_{21}} = \beta_{21} b^{c_1} = A(b, c)[4_1, +]$. Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$s_1 = \emptyset$.

$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\}$,

$d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}$, $w_{1.1} = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +]$, $d_{1.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_1 = 2$.

$x_1 = a_{21} = \{Per(b, f)[u, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1]\}$.

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = S_0.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}4_1], Per(b, f)[u, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

$$1.2.1.4.3. Y = \{y_1\}, y_1 = A(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1, +] \vee S(b, a)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1].$$

Поскольку $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0$, $X = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}4_1], Per(b, f)[u, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1], S(b, a)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}4_1]\}.$

$$1.2.1.4.4. \text{Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: } Q_4 = Q, S_4 = S, X_4 = X, Y_4 = Y.$$

$$1.2.1.5 Q_1 = 0 (Y_1 \neq \emptyset), Q_2 = 1, Q_3 = 0 (Y_3 \neq \emptyset), Q_4 = 0 (Y_4 \neq \emptyset). \text{Принимается } p_1 = 0.$$

1.2.2 Формируются множества дедуктивных, абдуктивных следствий и дополнительных фактов.

$$e_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$e'_1 = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]\}.$$

$$f_1 = \{Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}.$$

1.2.3 Формируется множество литералов описания схемы вывода и новый выводимый дизъюнкт.

$$z_1 = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}.$$

$$R_2 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +].$$

1.2.4 Фиксируются результаты выполнения процедуры.

1.3 Формирование семейств следствий, дополнительных фактов, описания схемы вывода и проверка признака.

$$s^1 = s^0 \cup \{e_1\} = \emptyset.$$

$$\pi^1 = \pi^0 \cup \{e'_1\} = \{\{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]\}\}.$$

$$\varphi^1 = \varphi^0 \cup \{f_1\} = \{\{Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}\}.$$

$$\eta^1 = \eta^0 \cup \{z_1\} = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}\}.$$

Поскольку $p_1 = 0$ и $h \neq H$, то вывод продолжается, $h = 2$.

1.4 Формируются исходные множества для процедуры вывода следующего шага.

$$c_2 = c_1 \cup e_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$c'_2 = c'_1 \cup e'_1 = \{F(a, c)[u, +], S(b, c)[u, +]\}.$$

$$g_2 = g_1 \cup f_1 = \{Per(a, m)[u, +], P(a, b)[u, +]\}.$$

$u_2 = M^F \cup M^N \cup c_1 \cup c'_1 \cup g_2 = \{P(c, d)[u, +], Per(b, f)[u, +], P(a, c)[u, +], N(b, c)[u, +],$
 $Per(a, m)[u, +], P(a, b)[u, +]\}.$

Переход к п. 2.

2.1. Выполняется процедура $\psi_2 = \langle M^D, R_2, u_2, o_2, p_2, R_3, f_2, z_2, \delta \rangle.$

2.1.1.1. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_1 = \langle D'_1, R_2, u_2, Q_1, S_1, X_1, Y_1 \rangle.$

$D'_1 = \langle Per(x, m)[+, 1_2] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1_2], F(x, y)[1_2, +], \theta \rangle, R_2 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee$
 $S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +].$

2.1.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_1, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle.$

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_1, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset.$

θ	$Per(x, m)[+, 1_2]$	$P(x, y)[+, 1_2]$
$F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]$	1	1

$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_1\}.$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x.$

2.1.1.1.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset.$

2.1.1.1.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_1 = Q, S_1 = S, X_1 = X, Y_1 = Y.$

2.1.1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_2 = \langle D'_2, R_2, u_2, Q_2, S_2, X_2, Y_2 \rangle.$

$D'_2 = \langle F(x, z)[+, 2_2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2_2], GF(x, y)[2_2, +], \theta \rangle, R_2 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee$
 $S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +].$

2.1.1.2.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_2, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle.$

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_2, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset.$

θ	$F(x, z)[+, 2_2]$	$P(z, y)[+, 2_2]$
$F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +]$	Δ_{11}	1
$S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{11} = \{a/x, c/z\}, \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, a_{11} = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2]\}, b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle,$
 $b^a_{11} = P(c, y)[+, 2_2], \beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{a/x, c/z\}, b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_2 = GF(a, y)[2_2, +].$ Принимается $q = 0.$

$s = \emptyset.$

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, w_1 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +], d^*_1 = 0.$

Принимается $q = 2.$

$x = a_{11} = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2]\}.$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = 0$, $d_1 = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +] \vee P(a, c)[u, +] \vee N(b, c)[u, +] \vee Per(a, m)[u, +] \vee P(a, b)[u, +]$.

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.2.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{a/x, c/z\}$	$P(c, y)[+, 2_2]$
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	1
$P(a, c)[u, +]$	1
$N(b, c)[u, +]$	1
$Per(a, m)[u, +]$	1
$P(a, b)[u, +]$	1

$\lambda_{11} = \{d/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$, $\beta_{11} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{11} = \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11} b^c_1 = GF(a, d)[2_2, +]$. Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$$s_1 = \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]\}.$$

$$n_1 = \emptyset, q_1 = 1.$$

$$x_1 = a_{11} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2]\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]\}.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2], P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

2.1.1.2.3. Поскольку $S \neq \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 0$, $X = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2], P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2]\}$.

2.1.1.2.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_2 = Q, S_2 = S, X_2 = X, Y_2 = Y$.

2.1.1.3. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_3 = \langle D'_3, R_2, u_2, Q_3, S_3, X_3, Y_3 \rangle$.

$D'_3 = \langle P(z, x)[+, 3_2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3_2] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3_2], S(x, y)[3_2, +], \theta \rangle$, $R_2 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]$.

2.1.1.3.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_3, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_3, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$P(z, x)[+, 3_2]$	$P(z, y)[+, 3_2]$	$N(x, y)[+, 3_2]$
$F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	1
$S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]$	1	1	1

$$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_3\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

2.1.1.3.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

2.1.1.3.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_3 = Q, S_3 = S, X_3 = X, Y_3 = Y$.

2.1.1.4. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_4 = \langle D'_4, R_2, u_2, Q_4, S_4, X_4, Y_4 \rangle$.

$$D'_4 = \langle Per(x, f)[+, 4_2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4_2] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4_2], A(x, y)[4_2, +], \theta \rangle, \quad R_2 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +].$$

2.1.1.4.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_4, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_4, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$Per(x, f)[+, 4_2]$	$P(z, y)[+, 4_2]$	$S(x, z)[+, 4_2]$
$F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	1
$S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}

$$\lambda_{23} = \{b/x, c/z\}, \quad \Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle, \quad a_{23} = \{S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2]\}, \quad b'_{23} = \langle b^a_{23}, b^c_{23}, \beta_{23} \rangle, \\ b^a_{23} = Per(b, f)[+, 4_2] \vee P(c, y)[+, 4_2], \quad \beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{b/x, c/z\}, \quad b^c_{23} = \beta_{23}D^c_4 = A(b, y)[4_2, +]. \quad \text{Принимается} \\ q = 0.$$

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, \quad d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, \quad w_1 = F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +], \quad d^*_1 = 0.$$

Принимается $q = 2$.

$$x = a_{23} = \{S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$,

$$d^*_1 = 0, \quad d_1 = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee Per(b, f)[u, +] \vee P(a, c)[u, +] \vee N(b, c)[u, +] \vee Per(a, m)[u, +] \vee P(a, b)[u, +],$$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, \quad h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.4.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{b/x, c/z\}$	$Per(b, f)[+, 4_2]$	$P(c, y)[+, 4_2]$
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{12}
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	Δ_{21}	1
$P(a, c)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(b, c)[u, +]$	1	1
$Per(a, m)[u, +]$	1	1
$P(a, b)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{12} = \{d/y\}$, $\Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle$, $a_{12} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{12} = \langle b^a_{12}, b^c_{12}, \beta_{12} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{12} = Per(b, f)[+, 4_2]$, $\beta_{12} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{12} = \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}$, $b^c_{12} = \beta_{12}b^c_1 = A(b, d)[4_2, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$\lambda_{21} = \emptyset$, $\Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle$, $a_{21} = \{Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{21} = \langle b^a_{21}, b^c_{21}, \beta_{21} \rangle$, $b^a_{21} = P(c, y)[+, 4_2]$,
 $\beta_{21} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{21} = \{b/x, c/z\}$, $b^c_{21} = \beta_{21}b^c_1 = A(b, y)[4_2, +]$. Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$s_1 = \emptyset$.

$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{1.2}, d_{1.2} \rangle\}$,

$d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}$, $w_{1.1} = P(c, d)[u, +] \vee P(a, c)[u, +] \vee N(b, c)[u, +] \vee Per(a, m)[u, +] \vee P(a, b)[u, +]$,

$d_{1.1} = Per(b, f)[u, +]$,

$d_{1.2} = d_1 \div w_{1.2}$, $w_{1.2} = Per(b, f)[u, +] \vee P(a, c)[u, +] \vee N(b, c)[u, +] \vee Per(a, m)[u, +] \vee P(a, b)[u, +]$,

$d_{1.2} = P(c, d)[u, +]$.

$x_1 = a_{12} \cup a_{21} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2]\}$.

$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = S_0$.

$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2],$

$Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2]\}$.

$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{1.2}, d_{1.2} \rangle\}$, $h = 1$.

2.1.1.4.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{1.1} = \langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1}, q_{1.1}, n_{1.1}, s_{1.1}, x_{1.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{1.1} = \emptyset$, $x_{1.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}$	$Per(b, f)[+, 4_2]$
$Per(b, f)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \emptyset$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$,

$\beta_{11} = \beta_{1.1} \cup \lambda_{11} = \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}b^c_{1.1} = A(b, d)[4_2, +]$. Принимается $q_{1.1} = 0$.

$s_{1.1} = \{A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}$.

$n_{1.1} = \emptyset$, $q_{1.1} = 1$.

$x_{1.1} = a_{11} = \{Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{1.2} = \langle b'_{1.2}, d_{1.2}, q_{1.2}, n_{1.2}, s_{1.2}, x_{1.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{1.2}, d_{1.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{1.2} = \emptyset$, $x_{1.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{b/x, c/z\}$	$P(c, y)[+, 4_2]$
$P(c, d)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \{d/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$,
 $\beta_{11} = \beta_{1.2} \cup \lambda_{11} = \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}b^c_{1.2} = A(b, d)[4_2, +]$. Принимается $q_{1.2} = 0$.

$s_{1.2} = \{A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}$.

$n_{1.2} = \emptyset$, $q_{1.2} = 1$.

$x_{1.2} = a_{11} = \{P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$.

$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{1.1} \cup s_{1.2} = \{A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}$.

$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{1.1} \cup x_{1.2} = \{S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2],$
 $Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$.

$n'_2 = \emptyset$, $S = S_2$, $X = X_2$.

2.1.1.4.3. Поскольку $S \neq \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 0$, $X = \{S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2],$
 $P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$.

2.1.1.4.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_4 = Q$, $S_4 = S$, $X_4 = X$, $Y_4 = Y$.

2.1.1.5 $Q_1 = 1$, $Q_2 = 0$ ($S_2 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_3 = 1$, $Q_4 = 0$ ($S_4 \neq \emptyset$). Принимается $p_2 = 0$.

2.1.2 **Формируются множества дедуктивных, абдуктивных следствий и дополнительных фактов.**

$e_2 = \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}$.

$e'_2 = \emptyset$.

$f_2 = \emptyset$.

2.1.3 **Формируется множество литералов описания схемы вывода и новый выводимый дизъюнкт.**

$z_2 = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2], P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2],$
 $P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}$.

$R_3 = GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +] \vee A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]$.

2.1.4 **Фиксируются результаты выполнения процедуры.**

2.2 **Формирование семейств следствий, дополнительных фактов, описания схемы вывода и проверка признака.**

$s^2 = s^1 \cup \{e_2\} = \{\{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}\}$.

$\pi^2 = \pi^1 \cup \{e'_2\} = \{\{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]\}\}$.

$$\varphi^2 = \varphi^1 \cup \{f_2\} = \{\{Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}\}.$$

$$\eta^2 = \eta^1 \cup \{z_2\} = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}, \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2], P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}\}.$$

Поскольку $p_2 = 0$ и $h \neq H$, то вывод продолжается, $h = 3$.

2.3 Формируются исходные множества для процедуры вывода следующего шага.

$$c_3 = c_2 \cup e_2 = \{GF(a, d)[u, +], A(b, d)[u, +]\}.$$

$$c'_3 = c'_2 \cup e'_2 = \{F(a, c)[u, +], S(b, c)[u, +]\}.$$

$$g_3 = g_2 \cup f_2 = \{Per(a, m)[u, +], P(a, b)[u, +]\}.$$

$$u_3 = M^F \cup M^N \cup c_2 \cup c'_2 \cup g_3 = \{P(c, d)[u, +], Per(b, f)[u, +], P(a, c)[u, +], N(b, c)[u, +], F(a, c)[u, +], S(b, c)[u, +], Per(a, m)[u, +], P(a, b)[u, +]\}.$$

Переход к п. 2.

3.1. Выполняется процедура $\psi_3 = \langle M^D, R_3, u_3, o_3, p_3, R_4, f_3, z_3, \delta \rangle$.

3.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\Omega_1 = \langle D'_1, R_3, u_3, Q_1, S_1, X_1, Y_1 \rangle$.

$$D'_1 = \langle Per(x, m)[+, 1_3] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1_3], F(x, y)[1_3, +], \theta \rangle, R_3 = GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +] \vee A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +].$$

3.1.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_1, R_3, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_1, R_3]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$Per(x, m)[+, 1_3]$	$P(x, y)[+, 1_3]$
$GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]$	1	1
$A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]$	1	1

$$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_1\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

3.1.1.1.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

3.1.1.1.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_1 = Q, S_1 = S, X_1 = X, Y_1 = Y$.

3.1.1.2. Выполняется процедура $\Omega_2 = \langle D'_2, R_3, u_3, Q_2, S_2, X_2, Y_2 \rangle$.

$$D'_2 = \langle F(x, z)[+, 2_3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2_3], GF(x, y)[2_3, +], \theta \rangle, R_3 = GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +] \vee A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +].$$

3.1.1.2.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_2, R_3, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_2, R_3]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$F(x, z)[+, 2_3]$	$P(z, y)[+, 2_3]$
$GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]$	1	1
$A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]$	1	1

$$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_2\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

3.1.1.2.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

3.1.1.2.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_2 = Q, S_2 = S, X_2 = X, Y_2 = Y$.

3.1.1.3. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_3 = \langle D'_3, R_3, u_3, Q_3, S_3, X_3, Y_3 \rangle$.

$$D'_3 = \langle P(z, x)[+, 3_3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3_3] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3_3], S(x, y)[3_3, +], \theta \rangle, R_3 = GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +] \vee A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +].$$

3.1.1.3.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_3, R_3, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_3, R_3]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$P(z, x)[+, 3_3]$	$P(z, y)[+, 3_3]$	$N(x, y)[+, 3_3]$
$GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]$	1	1	1
$A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]$	1	1	1

$$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_3\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

3.1.1.3.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

3.1.1.3.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_3 = Q, S_3 = S, X_3 = X, Y_3 = Y$.

3.1.1.4. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_4 = \langle D'_4, R_3, u_3, Q_4, S_4, X_4, Y_4 \rangle$.

$$D'_4 = \langle Per(x, f)[+, 4_3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4_3] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4_3], A(x, y)[4_3, +], \theta \rangle, R_3 = GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +] \vee A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +].$$

3.1.1.4.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_4, R_3, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_4, R_3]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$Per(x, f)[+, 4_3]$	$P(z, y)[+, 4_3]$	$S(x, z)[+, 4_3]$
$GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +]$	1	1	1
$A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]$	1	1	1

$$q = 1, n^* = \{\langle b'_1, 0 \rangle \mid b'_1 = D'_4\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s$, $X = x$.

3.1.1.4.2. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1$, $X = \emptyset$.

3.1.1.4.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_4 = Q$, $S_4 = S$, $X_4 = X$, $Y_4 = Y$.

3.1.1.5 $Q_1 = 1$, $Q_2 = 1$, $Q_3 = 1$, $Q_4 = 1$. Принимается $p_3 = 1$, $e_3 = e'_3 = f_3 = z_3 = \emptyset$, $R_4 = 0$.

3.1.2 **Фиксируются результаты выполнения процедуры.**

3.2 Формирование семейств следствий, дополнительных фактов, описания схемы вывода и проверка признака.

$$s^3 = s^2 \cup \{e_3\} = \{\{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}\}.$$

$$\pi^3 = \pi^2 \cup \{e'_3\} = \{\{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]\}\}.$$

$$\varphi^3 = \varphi^2 \cup \{f_3\} = \{\{Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}\}.$$

$$\eta^3 = \eta^2 \cup \{z_3\} = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1],$$

$$P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2],$$

$$P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2],$$

$$Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}\}.$$

Поскольку $p_3 = 1$ и $h = H = 3$, то вывод завершается.

3.3 Формирование общих множеств следствий, дополнительных фактов и описания схемы вывода.

$$M^E = \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +], F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, +],$$

$$S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, +]\}.$$

$$M^G = \{Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1]\}.$$

$$Z = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1],$$

$$P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2],$$

$$P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2],$$

$$Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}.$$

$$e^+ = \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}.$$

$$O = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \{a/x, c/y\}1_1], N(b, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1],$$

$$P(a, c)[n, \{b/x, c/y, a/z\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1], \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1_1, \{a/x, c/z\}2_2],$$

$$P(c, d)[u, \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, c/y, b/x\}3_1, \{b/x, c/z\}4_2], P(c, d)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2],$$

$$Per(b, f)[u, \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2]\}, \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2_2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4_2, +]\}\}.$$

Результаты выполнения процедур вывода представлены в таблице.

Перед построением схемы вывода с целью сокращения числа символов в параметрах литералов вводятся обозначения подстановок, используемых в литералах семейства множеств O : $\lambda_1 = \{a/x, c/y\}$, $\lambda_2 = \{a/z, c/y, b/x\}$, $\lambda_3 = \{a/x, c/z\}$, $\lambda_4 = \{a/x, c/z, d/y\}$, $\lambda_5 = \{b/x, c/z\}$, $\lambda_6 = \{b/x, c/z, d/y\}$, при этом $\lambda_3 \subseteq \lambda_4$, $\lambda_5 \subseteq \lambda_6$.

$O = \{ \{ P(a, c)[n, \lambda_1 1_1], Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_1 1_1], N(b, c)[n, \lambda_2 3_1], P(a, c)[n, \lambda_2 3_1], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_2 3_1] \},$
 $\{ F(a, c)[\lambda_1 1_1, \lambda_3 2_2], P(c, d)[u, \lambda_4 2_2], S(b, c)[\lambda_2 3_1, \lambda_5 4_2], P(c, d)[u, \lambda_6 4_2], Per(b, f)[u, \lambda_6 4_2] \},$
 $\{ GF(a, d)[\lambda_4 2_2, +], A(b, d)[\lambda_6 4_2, +] \} \}$.

Схема логического вывода следствий, построенная по описанию O , представлена на рисунке 1.

Рисунок 1 – Схема логического вывода следствий

Таким образом, в процессе вывода следствий было установлено, что при условии если Дмитрий – мужчина ($Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_1 1_1]$) и он является родителем Виктории ($P(a, b)[+, \lambda_2 3_1]$), то Дмитрий является отцом Владимира ($F(a, c)[\lambda_1 1_1, +]$), Владимир и Виктория – единокровные брат и сестра ($S(b, c)[\lambda_2 3_1, +]$), у Дмитрия есть внучка Наталья ($GF(a, d)[\lambda_4 2_2, +]$), а у Натальи – тетя Виктория ($A(b, d)[\lambda_6 4_2, +]$).

Таблица 1 – Результаты выполнения процедур вывода

Процедура вывода ψ_1 ($R_1 = P(a, c)[n, +] \vee N(b, c)[n, +], p_1 = 0, h = 1$)	
D'_1	$Q_1 = 0, S_1 = \emptyset, Y_1 = \{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, +] \vee Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}]\}, X_1 = \{P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{111}], Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}]\}$
D'_2	$Q_2 = 1, S_2 = \emptyset, Y_2 = \emptyset, X_2 = \emptyset$
D'_3	$Q_3 = 0, S_3 = \emptyset, Y_3 = \{S(c, c)[\{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1, +] \vee N(c, c)[+, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, +] \vee P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}, X_3 = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/x, c/y\}3_1], N(b, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], N(c, c)[+, \{a/z, c/y, c/x\}3_1], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}$
D'_4	$Q_4 = 0, S_4 = \emptyset, Y_4 = \{A(b, c)[\lambda_{241}, +] \vee S(b, a)[+, \lambda_{241}]\}, X_4 = \{P(a, c)[n, \{a/z, c/y\}4_1], Per(b, f)[u, \lambda_{241}], S(b, a)[+, \lambda_{241}]\}$
	$e_1 = \emptyset, e'_1 = \{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, +], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, +]\}, f_1 = \{Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}, z_1 = \{P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{111}], Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], N(b, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}$
	$s^1 = \emptyset, \pi^1 = \{\{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, +], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, +]\}\}, \varphi^1 = \{\{Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}\}, \eta^1 = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{111}], Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], N(b, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}\}$
Процедура вывода ψ_2 ($R_2 = F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, +] \vee S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, +], p_2 = 0, h = 2$)	
D'_1	$Q_1 = 1, S_1 = \emptyset, Y_1 = \emptyset, X_1 = \emptyset$
D'_2	$Q_2 = 0, S_2 = \{GF(a, d)[\lambda_{422}, +]\}, Y_2 = \emptyset, X_2 = \{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{322}], P(c, d)[5, \lambda_{422}]\}$
D'_3	$Q_3 = 1, S_3 = \emptyset, Y_3 = \emptyset, X_3 = \emptyset$
D'_4	$Q_4 = 0, S_4 = \{A(b, d)[\lambda_{642}, +]\}, Y_4 = \emptyset, X_4 = \{S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, \lambda_{542}], P(c, d)[u, \lambda_{642}], Per(b, f)[u, \lambda_{642}]\}$
	$e_2 = \{GF(a, d)[\lambda_{422}, +], A(b, d)[\lambda_{642}, +]\}, e'_2 = \emptyset, f_2 = \emptyset, z_2 = \{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{322}], P(c, d)[5, \lambda_{422}], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, \lambda_{542}], P(c, d)[u, \lambda_{642}], Per(b, f)[u, \lambda_{642}]\}$
	$s^2 = \{\{GF(a, d)[\lambda_{422}, +], A(b, d)[\lambda_{642}, +]\}\}, \pi^2 = \{\{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, +], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, +]\}\}, \varphi^2 = \{\{Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}\}, \eta^2 = \{\{P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{111}], Per(a, m)[+, \lambda_{111}], N(b, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, c)[n, \lambda_{231}], P(a, b)[+, \lambda_{231}]\}, \{F(a, c)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{322}], P(c, d)[5, \lambda_{422}], S(b, c)[\lambda_{231}, \lambda_{542}], P(c, d)[u, \lambda_{642}], Per(b, f)[u, \lambda_{642}]\}\}$
Процедура вывода ψ_3 ($R_3 = GF(a, d)[\lambda_{422}, +] \vee A(b, d)[\lambda_{642}, +], p_3 = 1, h = H = 3$)	
	$Q_{1-4} = 1, S_{1-4} = \emptyset, Y_{1-4} = \emptyset, X_{1-4} = \emptyset; e_3 = e'_3 = f_3 = z_3 = \emptyset; s^3 = s^2, \pi^3 = \pi^2, \varphi^3 = \varphi^2, \eta^3 = \eta^2$

Задача о сосудах с водой

Пусть даны пустые семи- и пятилитровый сосуды, необходимо найти все возможные пути заполнения сосудов (следствия) исходя из начального состояния. Для изменения состояния сосудов используются три типа действий: сосуд можно целиком заполнить, сосуд можно целиком опустошить, жидкость можно перелить из одного сосуда в другой так, что либо первый сосуд станет пустым, либо второй целиком заполнится.

Воспользуемся формальным описанием из работы [Ковальски Р. Логика в решении проблем / Пер. с англ. – М.: Наука, 1990. – 280 с.]. Будем считать, что предикат $S(u, v)$ обозначает состояние, при котором в семилитровом сосуде находится u литров жидкости, а в пятилитровом – v литров. Отношение $x + y = z$ представим предикатом $R(x, y, z)$, который принимает значение «истина», если $x + y = z$ и «ложь» – в противном случае. Отношение $x \leq y$ представим предикатом $N(x, y)$, который принимает значение «истина», если $x \leq y$ и «ложь» – в противном случае. Будем также считать, что частично эти отношения уже заданы, что обеспечивает неполноту исходной базы знаний. Тогда формальное описание задачи представляется в следующем виде.

$$1) 1 \rightarrow R(5, 2, 7);$$

$$2) 1 \rightarrow N(5, 7);$$

$$3) S(x, y) \rightarrow S(7, y);$$

$$4) S(x, y) \rightarrow S(x, 5);$$

$$5) S(x, y) \rightarrow S(0, y);$$

$$6) S(x, y) \rightarrow S(x, 0);$$

$$7) R(u, v, y) \& N(y, 5) \& S(u, v) \rightarrow S(0, y);$$

$$8) R(u, v, x) \& N(x, 7) \& S(u, v) \rightarrow S(x, 0);$$

$$9) R(u, v, w) \& R(7, y, w) \& S(u, v) \rightarrow S(7, y);$$

$$10) R(u, v, w) \& R(5, x, w) \& S(u, v) \rightarrow S(x, 5);$$

Новые факты:

$$11) 1 \rightarrow S(0, 0);$$

Правила 3 и 4 определяют действия по заполнению сосудов извне, 5 и 6 – по опустошению сосудов. Правила 7 и 8 задают действия по переливанию из одного сосуда в другой до тех пор, пока первый не станет пустым, а 9 и 10 – пока второй не станет полный.

Преобразуем посылки и новые факты в дизъюнкты.

$$F_1 = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +];$$

$$F_2 = N(5, 7)[u, +];$$

$$D_1 = S(7, y)[1, +] \vee S(x, y)[+, 1], D'_1 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 1], S(7, y)[1, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_2 = S(x, 5)[2, +] \vee S(x, y)[+, 2], D'_2 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 2], S(x, 5)[2, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_3 = S(0, y)[3, +] \vee S(x, y)[+, 3], D'_3 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 3], S(0, y)[3, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_4 = S(x, 0)[4, +] \vee S(x, y)[+, 4], D'_4 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 4], S(x, 0)[4, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_5 = S(0, y)[5, +] \vee R(u, v, y)[+, 5] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5] \vee S(u, v)[+, 5],$$

$$D'_5 = \langle R(u, v, y)[+, 5] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5] \vee S(u, v)[+, 5], S(0, y)[5, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_6 = S(x, 0)[6, +] \vee R(u, v, x)[+, 6] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6] \vee S(u, v)[+, 6],$$

$$D'_6 = \langle R(u, v, x)[+, 6] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6] \vee S(u, v)[+, 6], S(x, 0)[6, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_7 = S(7, y)[7, +] \vee R(u, v, w)[+, 7] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7] \vee S(u, v)[+, 7],$$

$$D'_7 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 7] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7] \vee S(u, v)[+, 7], S(7, y)[7, +], \theta \rangle;$$

$$D_8 = S(x, 5)[8, +] \vee R(u, v, w)[+, 8] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8] \vee S(u, v)[+, 8],$$

$$D'_8 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 8] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8] \vee S(u, v)[+, 8], S(x, 5)[8, +], \theta \rangle.$$

$$N_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

Логический вывод будет состоять из следующих шагов.

1.1. **Определяются начальные значения.** $h = 1$, $M^D = \{D'_1, D'_2, D'_3, D'_4, D'_5, D'_6, D'_7, D'_8\}$,
 $M^N = \{N_1\} = \{S(0, 0)[n, +]\}$, $H = \gamma = 2$, $n_{max} = \delta = 2$, $R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +]$. Определяются начальные
множества: $e_0 = M^F \bar{\cap} M^N = \emptyset$, $s^0 = \{e_0\}$, $c_1 = e_0$, $\pi^0 = \emptyset$, $c'_1 = \emptyset$, $\phi^0 = \emptyset$, $g_1 = \emptyset$, $\eta^0 = \emptyset$,
 $u_1 = M^F = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, +], N(5, 7)[u, +]\}$.

1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\psi_1 = \langle M^D, R_1, u_1, o_1, p_1, R_2, f_1, z_1, \delta \rangle$.

1.2.1.1. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_1 = \langle D'_1, R_1, u_1, Q_1, S_1, X_1, Y_1 \rangle$.

$$D'_1 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 1_1], S(7, y)[1_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

1.2.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_1, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_1, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 1_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$,
 $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11} D^c_1 = S(7, 0)[1_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]\}.$$

$$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$$

$$x = a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s$, $X = x$.

1.2.1.1.2. $Y = \emptyset$, $Q = 0$, $X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1]\}$.

1.2.1.1.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_1 = Q$, $S_1 = S$, $X_1 = X$, $Y_1 = Y$.

1.2.1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_2 = \langle D'_2, R_1, u_1, Q_2, S_2, X_2, Y_2 \rangle$.

$$D'_2 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 2_1], S(x, 5)[2_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

1.2.1.2.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_2, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_2, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 2_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \quad \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, \quad a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1]\}, \quad b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, \quad b^a_{11} = 0,$
 $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \quad b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_2 = S(0, 5)[2_1, +].$ Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]\}.$

$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$

$x = a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1]\}.$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

1.2.1.2.2. $Y = \emptyset, Q = 0, X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1]\}.$

1.2.1.2.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_2 = Q, S_2 = S, X_2 = X, Y_2 = Y$.

1.2.1.3. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_3 = \langle D'_3, R_1, u_1, Q_3, S_3, X_3, Y_3 \rangle$.

$D'_3 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 3_1], S(0, y)[3_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$

1.2.1.3.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_3, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_3, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 3_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \quad \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, \quad a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1]\}, \quad b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, \quad b^a_{11} = 0,$
 $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \quad b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_3 = S(0, 0)[3_1, +].$ Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]\}.$

$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$

$x = a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1]\}.$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

1.2.1.3.2. $Y = \emptyset, Q = 0, X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1]\}.$

1.2.1.3.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_3 = Q, S_3 = S, X_3 = X, Y_3 = Y$.

1.2.1.4. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_4 = \langle D'_4, R_1, u_1, Q_4, S_4, X_4, Y_4 \rangle$.

$D'_4 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 4_1], S(x, 0)[4_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$

1.2.1.4.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_4, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_4, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 4_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	Δ_{11}

$\lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$, $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_4 = S(0, 0)[4_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]\}.$$

$$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$$

$$x = a_{11} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s$, $X = x$.

$$1.2.1.4.2. Y = \emptyset, Q = 0, X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1]\}.$$

$$1.2.1.4.3. \text{Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: } Q_4 = Q, S_4 = S, X_4 = X, Y_4 = Y.$$

$$1.2.1.5. \text{Выполняется процедура } \Omega_5 = \langle D'_5, R_1, u_1, Q_5, S_5, X_5, Y_5 \rangle.$$

$$D'_5 = \langle R(u, v, y)[+, 5_1] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_1] \vee S(u, v)[+, 5_1], S(0, y)[5_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

$$1.2.1.5.1. \text{Выполняется процедура } \omega = \langle D'_5, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle.$$

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_5, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, y)[+, 5_1]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_1]$	$S(u, v)[+, 5_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}

$\lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}$, $\Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle$, $a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_1]\}$, $b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle$, $b^a_{13} = R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_1] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_1]$, $\beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}$, $b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1, w_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +], d^*_1 = 0. \text{ Принимается } q = 2.$$

$$x = a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = 0$, $d_1 = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$.

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

$$1.2.1.5.2. \text{Выполняется процедура } \omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle.$$

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_1]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_1]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_1]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

1.2.1.5.3. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

1.2.1.5.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_5 = Q, S_5 = S, X_5 = X, Y_5 = Y$.

1.2.1.6. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_6 = \langle D'_6, R_1, u_1, Q_6, S_6, X_6, Y_6 \rangle$.

$$D'_6 = \langle R(u, v, x)[+, 6_1] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_1] \vee S(u, v)[+, 6_1], S(x, 0)[6_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

1.2.1.6.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_6, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_6, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, x)[+, 6_1]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_1]$	$S(u, v)[+, 6_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}

$$\lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, \quad a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1]\}, \quad b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{13} = R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_1] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_1], \quad \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_1, +]. \text{ Принимается}$$

$$q = 0.$$

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1, w_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +], d^*_1 = 0. \text{ Принимается } q = 2.$$

$$x = a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = 0, d_1 = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$.

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

1.2.1.6.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_1]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_1]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{22}

$$\lambda_{22} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{22} = \langle a_{22}, b'_{22} \rangle, \quad a_{22} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1]\}, \quad b'_{22} = \langle b^a_{22}, b^c_{22}, \beta_{22} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{22} = R(0, 0, 5)[+, 6_1], \quad \beta_{22} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{22} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, \quad b^c_{22} = \beta_{22}b^c_1 = S(5, 0)[6_1, +]. \text{ Принимается } q_1 = 0.$$

$$s_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\}, d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}, w_{1.1} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +], d_{1.1} = 0. \text{ Принимается } q_1 = 2.$$

$$x_1 = a_{22} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1]\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

$$1.2.1.6.3. Y = \{y_1\}, y_1 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1].$$

$$Q = 0, X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1]\}.$$

$$1.2.1.6.4. \text{Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: } Q_6 = Q, S_6 = S, X_6 = X, Y_6 = Y.$$

$$1.2.1.7. \text{Выполняется процедура } \Omega_7 = \langle D'_7, R_1, u_1, Q_7, S_7, X_7, Y_7 \rangle.$$

$$D'_7 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 7_1] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_1] \vee S(u, v)[+, 7_1], S(7, y)[7_1, +], \theta \rangle, R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +].$$

$$1.2.1.7.1. \text{Выполняется процедура } \omega = \langle D'_7, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle.$$

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_7, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, w)[+, 7_1]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_1]$	$S(u, v)[+, 7_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}

$$\lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, \quad a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_1]\}, \quad b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{13} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_1] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_1], \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_1, +]. \text{Принимается}$$

$$q = 0.$$

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1, w_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +], d^*_1 = 0. \text{Принимается } q = 2.$$

$$x = a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_1]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}, d^*_1 = 0, d_1 = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +].$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

$$1.2.1.7.2. \text{Выполняется процедура } \omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle.$$

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_1]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_1]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_1]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

1.2.1.7.3. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1$, $X = \emptyset$.

1.2.1.7.4. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_7 = Q$, $S_7 = S$, $X_7 = X$, $Y_7 = Y$.

1.2.1.8. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_8 = \langle D'_8, R_1, u_1, Q_8, S_8, X_8, Y_8 \rangle$.

$D'_8 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 8_1] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_1] \vee S(u, v)[+, 8_1], S(x, 5)[8_1, +], \theta \rangle$, $R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +]$.

1.2.1.8.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_8, R_1, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_8, R_1]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, w)[+, 8_1]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_1]$	$S(u, v)[+, 8_1]$
$S(0, 0)[n, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}

$\lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}$, $\Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle$, $a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1]\}$, $b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle$,

$b^a_{13} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_1] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_1]$, $\beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{0/u, 0/v\}$, $b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_1, +]$. Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = R_1 \div w_1$, $w_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +]$, $d^*_1 = 0$. Принимается $q = 2$.

$x = a_{13} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1]\}$.

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle\}$, $d^*_1 = 0$, $d_1 = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$.

$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle\}$, $h = 0$, $S_0 = s$, $X_0 = x$.

1.2.1.8.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset$, $x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_1]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_1]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{12}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{12} = \{2/x, 7/w\}$, $\Delta_{12} = \langle a_{12}, b'_{12} \rangle$, $a_{12} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}$, $b'_{12} = \langle b^a_{12}, b^c_{12}, \beta_{12} \rangle$,

$b^a_{12} = R(0, 0, 7)[+, 8_1]$, $\beta_{12} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{12} = \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$, $b^c_{12} = \beta_{12}b^c_1 = S(2, 5)[8_1, +]$. Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$s_1 = \emptyset$.

$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\}$, $d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}$, $w_{1.1} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$, $d_{1.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_1 = 2$.

$x_1 = a_{12} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}$.

$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 = \emptyset$.

$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}$.

$$n'_1 = \emptyset, S = S_1, X = X_1.$$

$$1.2.1.8.3. Y = \{y_1\}, y_1 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1].$$

$$Q = 0, \quad X = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}.$$

$$1.2.1.8.4. \text{Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: } Q_8 = Q, S_8 = S, X_8 = X, Y_8 = Y.$$

$$1.2.1.9 \quad Q_1 = 0 \ (S_1 \neq \emptyset), \quad Q_2 = 0 \ (S_2 \neq \emptyset), \quad Q_3 = 0 \ (S_3 \neq \emptyset), \quad Q_4 = 0 \ (S_4 \neq \emptyset), \quad Q_5 = 1, \quad Q_6 = 0 \ (Y_6 \neq \emptyset), \\ Q_7 = 1, \quad Q_8 = 0 \ (Y_8 \neq \emptyset). \text{ Принимается } p_1 = 0.$$

1.2.2 Формируются множества дедуктивных, абдуктивных следствий и дополнительных фактов.

$$e_1 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]\}.$$

$$e'_1 = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]\}.$$

$$f_1 = \{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}.$$

1.2.3 Формируется множество литералов описания схемы вывода и новый выводимый дизъюнкт.

$$z_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1], \\ S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1], \\ R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}.$$

$$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

1.2.4 Фиксируются результаты выполнения процедуры.

1.3 Формирование семейств следствий, дополнительных фактов, описания схемы вывода и проверка признака.

$$s^1 = s^0 \cup \{e_1\} = \{\{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], \\ S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]\}\}.$$

$$\pi^1 = \pi^0 \cup \{e'_1\} = \{\{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]\}\}.$$

$$\varphi^1 = \varphi^0 \cup \{f_1\} = \{\{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}\}.$$

$$\eta^1 = \eta^0 \cup \{z_1\} = \{\{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1], \\ S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], \\ S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1]\}\}.$$

Поскольку $p_1 = 0$ и $h \neq H$, то вывод продолжается, $h = 2$.

1.4 Формируются исходные множества для процедуры вывода следующего шага.

$$c_2 = c_1 \cup e_1 = \{S(7, 0)[u, +], S(0, 5)[u, +], S(0, 0)[u, +], S(0, 0)[u, +]\}.$$

$$c'_2 = c'_1 \cup e'_1 = \{S(5, 0)[u, +], S(2, 5)[u, +]\}.$$

$$g_2 = g_1 \cup f_1 = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]\}.$$

$$u_2 = M^F \cup M^N \cup c_1 \cup c'_1 \cup g_2 = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, +], N(5, 7)[u, +], S(0, 0)[u, +], R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]\}.$$

Переход к п. 2.

2.1. Выполняется процедура $\psi_1 = \langle M^D, R_2, u_2, o_2, p_2, R_3, f_2, z_2, \delta \rangle$.

2.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\Omega_1 = \langle D'_1, R_2, u_2, Q_1, S_1, X_1, Y_1 \rangle$.

$$D'_1 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 1_2], S(7, y)[1_2, +], \theta \rangle,$$

$$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

2.1.1.1.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_1, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_1, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 1_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	Δ_{11}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	Δ_{21}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	Δ_{31}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	Δ_{41}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	Δ_{51}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	Δ_{61}

$$\lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, a_{11} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, b^a_{11} = 0, \beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_1 = S(7, 0)[1_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, \Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle, a_{21} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{21} = \langle b^a_{21}, b^c_{21}, \beta_{21} \rangle, b^a_{21} = 0, \beta_{21} = \lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, b^c_{21} = \beta_{21}D^c_1 = S(7, 5)[1_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{31} = \langle a_{31}, b'_{31} \rangle, a_{31} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{31} = \langle b^a_{31}, b^c_{31}, \beta_{31} \rangle, b^a_{31} = 0, \beta_{31} = \lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{31} = \beta_{31}D^c_1 = S(7, 0)[1_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{41} = \langle a_{41}, b'_{41} \rangle, a_{41} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{41} = \langle b^a_{41}, b^c_{41}, \beta_{41} \rangle, b^a_{41} = 0, \beta_{41} = \lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{41} = \beta_{41}D^c_1 = S(7, 0)[1_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{51} = \langle a_{51}, b'_{51} \rangle, a_{51} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{51} = \langle b^a_{51}, b^c_{51}, \beta_{51} \rangle, b^a_{51} = 0, \beta_{51} = \lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{51} = \beta_{51}D^c_1 = S(7, 0)[1_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}, \Delta_{61} = \langle a_{61}, b'_{61} \rangle, a_{61} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2]\}, b'_{61} = \langle b^a_{61}, b^c_{61}, \beta_{61} \rangle, b^a_{61} = 0, \beta_{61} = \lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}, b^c_{61} = \beta_{61}D^c_1 = S(7, 5)[1_2, +].$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}1_2, +]\}.$

$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$

$x = a_{11} \cup a_{21} \cup a_{31} \cup a_{41} \cup a_{51} \cup a_{61} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2]\}.$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x.$

2.1.1.1.2. $S \neq \emptyset, Y = \emptyset, Q = 0, X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2]\}.$

2.1.1.1.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_1 = Q, S_1 = S, X_1 = X, Y_1 = Y.$

2.1.1.2. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_2 = \langle D'_2, R_2, u_2, Q_2, S_2, X_2, Y_2 \rangle.$

$D'_2 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 2_2], S(x, 5)[2_2, +], \emptyset \rangle,$

$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$

2.1.1.2.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_2, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle.$

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_2, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset.$

$\emptyset$	$S(x, y)[+, 2_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	Δ_{11}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	Δ_{21}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	Δ_{31}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	Δ_{41}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	Δ_{51}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	Δ_{61}

$\lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, a_{11} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, b^a_{11} = 0, \beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_2 = S(7, 5)[2_2, +].$

$\lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, \Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle, a_{21} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{21} = \langle b^a_{21}, b^c_{21}, \beta_{21} \rangle, b^a_{21} = 0, \beta_{21} = \lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, b^c_{21} = \beta_{21}D^c_2 = S(0, 5)[2_2, +].$

$\lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{31} = \langle a_{31}, b'_{31} \rangle, a_{31} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{31} = \langle b^a_{31}, b^c_{31}, \beta_{31} \rangle, b^a_{31} = 0, \beta_{31} = \lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{31} = \beta_{31}D^c_2 = S(0, 5)[2_2, +].$

$\lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{41} = \langle a_{41}, b'_{41} \rangle, a_{41} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{41} = \langle b^a_{41}, b^c_{41}, \beta_{41} \rangle, b^a_{41} = 0, \beta_{41} = \lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}, b^c_{41} = \beta_{41}D^c_2 = S(0, 5)[2_2, +].$

$$\lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{51} = \langle a_{51}, b'_{51} \rangle, a_{51} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{51} = \langle b^{a_{51}}, b^{c_{51}}, \beta_{51} \rangle, b^{a_{51}} = 0, \beta_{51} = \lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}, b^{c_{51}} = \beta_{51}D^c_2 = S(5, 5)[2_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}, \Delta_{61} = \langle a_{61}, b'_{61} \rangle, a_{61} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}2_2]\}, b'_{61} = \langle b^{a_{61}}, b^{c_{61}}, \beta_{61} \rangle, b^{a_{61}} = 0, \beta_{61} = \lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}, b^{c_{61}} = \beta_{61}D^c_2 = S(2, 5)[2_2, +].$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \{S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}2_2, +]\}.$$

$$n = \emptyset, q = 1.$$

$$x = a_{11} \cup a_{21} \cup a_{31} \cup a_{41} \cup a_{51} \cup a_{61} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}2_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s, X = x$.

$$2.1.1.2.2. S \neq \emptyset, Y = \emptyset, Q = 0, X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}2_2]\}.$$

2.1.1.2.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_2 = Q, S_2 = S, X_2 = X, Y_2 = Y$.

2.1.1.3. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_3 = \langle D'_3, R_2, u_2, Q_3, S_3, X_3, Y_3 \rangle$.

$$D'_3 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 3_2], S(0, y)[3_2, +], \theta \rangle,$$

$$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

2.1.1.3.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_3, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_3, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 3_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	Δ_{11}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	Δ_{21}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	Δ_{31}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	Δ_{41}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	Δ_{51}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	Δ_{61}

$$\lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, a_{11} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}3_2]\}, b'_{11} = \langle b^{a_{11}}, b^{c_{11}}, \beta_{11} \rangle, b^{a_{11}} = 0, \beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}, b^{c_{11}} = \beta_{11}D^c_3 = S(0, 0)[3_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, \Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle, a_{21} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}3_2]\}, b'_{21} = \langle b^{a_{21}}, b^{c_{21}}, \beta_{21} \rangle, b^{a_{21}} = 0, \beta_{21} = \lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}, b^{c_{21}} = \beta_{21}D^c_3 = S(0, 5)[3_2, +].$$

$\lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{31} = \langle a_{31}, b'_{31} \rangle$, $a_{31} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2]\}$, $b'_{31} = \langle b^a_{31}, b^c_{31}, \beta_{31} \rangle$, $b^a_{31} = 0$, $\beta_{31} = \lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{31} = \beta_{31}D^c_3 = S(0, 0)[3_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{41} = \langle a_{41}, b'_{41} \rangle$, $a_{41} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2]\}$, $b'_{41} = \langle b^a_{41}, b^c_{41}, \beta_{41} \rangle$, $b^a_{41} = 0$, $\beta_{41} = \lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{41} = \beta_{41}D^c_3 = S(0, 0)[3_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{51} = \langle a_{51}, b'_{51} \rangle$, $a_{51} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}3_2]\}$, $b'_{51} = \langle b^a_{51}, b^c_{51}, \beta_{51} \rangle$, $b^a_{51} = 0$, $\beta_{51} = \lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{51} = \beta_{51}D^c_3 = S(0, 0)[3_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}$, $\Delta_{61} = \langle a_{61}, b'_{61} \rangle$, $a_{61} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}3_2]\}$, $b'_{61} = \langle b^a_{61}, b^c_{61}, \beta_{61} \rangle$, $b^a_{61} = 0$, $\beta_{61} = \lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}$, $b^c_{61} = \beta_{61}D^c_3 = S(0, 5)[3_2, +]$.

Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \{S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}3_2, +]\}$.

$n = \emptyset$, $q = 1$.

$x = a_{11} \cup a_{21} \cup a_{31} \cup a_{41} \cup a_{51} \cup a_{61} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}3_2]\}$.

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s$, $X = x$.

2.1.1.3.2. $S \neq \emptyset$, $Y = \emptyset$, $Q = 0$, $X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}3_2]\}$.

2.1.1.3.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_3 = Q$, $S_3 = S$, $X_3 = X$, $Y_3 = Y$.

2.1.1.4. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_4 = \langle D'_4, R_2, u_2, Q_4, S_4, X_4, Y_4 \rangle$.

$D'_4 = \langle S(x, y)[+, 4_2], S(x, 0)[4_2, +], \theta \rangle$,

$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$.

2.1.1.4.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_4, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_4, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

θ	$S(x, y)[+, 4_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	Δ_{11}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	Δ_{21}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	Δ_{31}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	Δ_{41}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	Δ_{51}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	Δ_{61}

$\lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle$, $a_{11} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle$, $b^a_{11} = 0$, $\beta_{11} = \lambda_{11} = \{7/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}D^c_4 = S(7, 0)[4_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}$, $\Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle$, $a_{21} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{21} = \langle b^a_{21}, b^c_{21}, \beta_{21} \rangle$, $b^a_{21} = 0$, $\beta_{21} = \lambda_{21} = \{0/x, 5/y\}$, $b^c_{21} = \beta_{21}D^c_4 = S(0, 0)[4_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{31} = \langle a_{31}, b'_{31} \rangle$, $a_{31} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{31} = \langle b^a_{31}, b^c_{31}, \beta_{31} \rangle$, $b^a_{31} = 0$, $\beta_{31} = \lambda_{31} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{31} = \beta_{31}D^c_4 = S(0, 0)[4_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{41} = \langle a_{41}, b'_{41} \rangle$, $a_{41} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{41} = \langle b^a_{41}, b^c_{41}, \beta_{41} \rangle$, $b^a_{41} = 0$, $\beta_{41} = \lambda_{41} = \{0/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{41} = \beta_{41}D^c_4 = S(0, 0)[4_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}$, $\Delta_{51} = \langle a_{51}, b'_{51} \rangle$, $a_{51} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{51} = \langle b^a_{51}, b^c_{51}, \beta_{51} \rangle$, $b^a_{51} = 0$, $\beta_{51} = \lambda_{51} = \{5/x, 0/y\}$, $b^c_{51} = \beta_{51}D^c_4 = S(5, 0)[4_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}$, $\Delta_{61} = \langle a_{61}, b'_{61} \rangle$, $a_{61} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}4_2]\}$, $b'_{61} = \langle b^a_{61}, b^c_{61}, \beta_{61} \rangle$, $b^a_{61} = 0$, $\beta_{61} = \lambda_{61} = \{2/x, 5/y\}$, $b^c_{61} = \beta_{61}D^c_4 = S(2, 0)[4_2, +]$.

Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}4_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}4_2, +]\}$.

$n = \emptyset$, $q = 1$.

$x = a_{11} \cup a_{21} \cup a_{31} \cup a_{41} \cup a_{51} \cup a_{61} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}4_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}4_2]\}$.

Поскольку $q = 1$, то $S = s$, $X = x$.

2.1.1.4.2. $S \neq \emptyset$, $Y = \emptyset$, $Q = 0$, $X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}4_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}4_2]\}$.

2.1.1.4.3. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_4 = Q$, $S_4 = S$, $X_4 = X$, $Y_4 = Y$.

2.1.1.5. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_5 = \langle D'_5, R_2, u_2, Q_5, S_5, X_5, Y_5 \rangle$.

$$D'_5 = \langle R(u, v, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2] \vee S(u, v)[+, 5_2], S(0, y)[5_2, +], \theta \rangle,$$

$$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

2.1.1.5.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_5, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_5, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$	$S(u, v)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{33}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{43}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{53}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{63}

$$\lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, \quad a_{13} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle, \\ b^a_{13} = R(7, 0, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle, \quad a_{23} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{23} = \langle b^a_{23}, b^c_{23}, \beta_{23} \rangle, \\ b^a_{23} = R(0, 5, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, b^c_{23} = \beta_{23}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{33} = \langle a_{33}, b'_{33} \rangle, \quad a_{33} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{33} = \langle b^a_{33}, b^c_{33}, \beta_{33} \rangle, \\ b^a_{33} = R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \beta_{33} = \lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{33} = \beta_{33}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{43} = \langle a_{43}, b'_{43} \rangle, \quad a_{43} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{43} = \langle b^a_{43}, b^c_{43}, \beta_{43} \rangle, \\ b^a_{43} = R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \beta_{43} = \lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{43} = \beta_{43}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{53} = \langle a_{53}, b'_{53} \rangle, \quad a_{53} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{53} = \langle b^a_{53}, b^c_{53}, \beta_{53} \rangle, \\ b^a_{53} = R(5, 0, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \beta_{53} = \lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{53} = \beta_{53}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{63} = \langle a_{63}, b'_{63} \rangle, \quad a_{63} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}5_2]\}, \\ b'_{63} = \langle b^a_{63}, b^c_{63}, \beta_{63} \rangle, \quad b^a_{63} = R(2, 5, y)[+, 5_2] \vee N(y, 5)[+, 5_2], \quad \beta_{63} = \lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \\ b^c_{63} = \beta_{63}D^c_5 = S(0, y)[5_2, +].$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\},$$

$$d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, \quad w_1 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], \quad d^*_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_2 = R_2 \div w_2, \quad w_2 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], \quad d^*_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_3 = R_2 \div w_3, \quad w_3 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], \quad d^*_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_4 = R_2 \div w_4, \quad w_4 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +], \quad d^*_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_5 = R_2 \div w_5, \quad w_5 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], \quad d^*_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_6 = R_2 \div w_6, \quad w_6 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +], \quad d^*_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +].$$

$$x = a_{13} \cup a_{23} \cup a_{33} \cup a_{43} \cup a_{53} \cup a_{63} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}5_2], \\ S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}5_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2], \\ S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}5_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}5_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\}$,

$$d_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d_6 \rangle\}, \quad h = 0, \quad S_0 = s, \quad X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.5.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{7/u, 0/v\}$	$R(7, 0, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_2 = \langle b'_2, d_2, q_2, n_2, s_2, x_2 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_2, d_2]$ и устанавливается $s_2 = \emptyset, x_2 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 5/v\}$	$R(0, 5, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_2 = 1, n_2 = \{\langle b'_{2.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{2.1} = b'_2\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_3 = \langle b'_3, d_3, q_3, n_3, s_3, x_3 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_3, d_3]$ и устанавливается $s_3 = \emptyset, x_3 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/y\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{81} = N(5, 5)[+, 5_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_3 = S(0, 5)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/y\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{91} = N(7, 5)[+, 5_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_3 = S(0, 7)[5_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_3 = 0$.

$$s_3 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_3 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{3.1} = d_3 \div w_{3.1}, \quad w_{3.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \quad d_{3.1} = R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.2} = d_3 \div w_{3.2}, \quad w_{3.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{3.2} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_3 = a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_4 = \langle b'_4, d_4, q_4, n_4, s_4, x_4 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_4, d_4]$ и устанавливается $s_4 = \emptyset, x_4 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/y\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{81} = N(5, 5)[+, 5_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_4 = S(0, 5)[5_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/y\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{91} = N(7, 5)[+, 5_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_4 = S(0, 7)[5_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_4 = 0$.

$$s_4 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_4 = \{\langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{4.1} = d_4 \div w_{4.1}, \quad w_{4.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \quad d_{4.1} = R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.2} = d_4 \div w_{4.2}, \quad w_{4.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{4.2} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_4 = a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_5 = \langle b'_5, d_5, q_5, n_5, s_5, x_5 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_5, d_5]$ и устанавливается $s_5 = \emptyset, x_5 = \emptyset$.

$\{5/u, 0/v\}$	$R(5, 0, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_5 = 1, n_5 = \{\langle b'_{5.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{5.1} = b'_5\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_6 = \langle b'_6, d_6, q_6, n_6, s_6, x_6 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_6, d_6]$ и устанавливается $s_6 = \emptyset, x_6 = \emptyset$.

$\{2/u, 5/v\}$	$R(2, 5, y)[+, 5_2]$	$N(y, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_6 = 1, n_6 = \{\langle b'_{6.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{6.1} = b'_6\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 \cup s_2 \cup s_3 \cup s_4 \cup s_5 \cup s_6 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 \cup x_2 \cup x_3 \cup x_4 \cup x_5 \cup x_6 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}5_2],$$

$$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}5_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2],$$

$$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}5_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}5_2],$$

$$R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle\}, \text{ т.к. } \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle.$$

$$h = 1.$$

2.1.1.5.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.1} = \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}, q_{3.1}, n_{3.1}, s_{3.1}, x_{3.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.1} = \emptyset, x_{3.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}$	$N(5, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1

$q_{3.1} = 1, n_{3.1} = \{\langle b'_{3.1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.1.1} = b'_{3.1}\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.2} = \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}, q_{3.2}, n_{3.2}, s_{3.2}, x_{3.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.2} = \emptyset, x_{3.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}$	$N(7, 5)[+, 5_2]$
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1

$q_{3.2} = 1, n_{3.2} = \{\langle b'_{3.2.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.2.1} = b'_{3.2}\}$.

$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{3.1} \cup s_{3.2} = S_1 = \emptyset$.

$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{3.1} \cup x_{3.2} = X_1$.

$n'_2 = \emptyset, S = S_2, X = X_2$.

2.1.1.5.4. $Y = \{y_1, y_2\}, y_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2, +] \vee N(5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2],$

$y_2 = S(0, 7)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2, +] \vee N(7, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2].$

Поскольку $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0, X = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}5_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2], N(5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], N(7, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}$.

2.1.1.5.5. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_5 = Q, S_5 = S, X_5 = X, Y_5 = Y$.

2.1.1.6. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_6 = \langle D'_6, R_2, u_2, Q_6, S_6, X_6, Y_6 \rangle$.

$D'_6 = \langle R(u, v, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2] \vee S(u, v)[+, 6_2], S(x, 0)[6_2, +], \theta \rangle,$

$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$

2.1.1.6.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_6, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_6, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$	$S(u, v)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{33}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{43}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{53}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{63}

$$\lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, \quad a_{13} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle, \\ b^a_{13} = R(7, 0, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, \quad b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle, \quad a_{23} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{23} = \langle b^a_{23}, b^c_{23}, \beta_{23} \rangle, \\ b^a_{23} = R(0, 5, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, \quad b^c_{23} = \beta_{23}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{33} = \langle a_{33}, b'_{33} \rangle, \quad a_{33} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{33} = \langle b^a_{33}, b^c_{33}, \beta_{33} \rangle, \\ b^a_{33} = R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{33} = \lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad b^c_{33} = \beta_{33}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{43} = \langle a_{43}, b'_{43} \rangle, \quad a_{43} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{43} = \langle b^a_{43}, b^c_{43}, \beta_{43} \rangle, \\ b^a_{43} = R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{43} = \lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad b^c_{43} = \beta_{43}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{53} = \langle a_{53}, b'_{53} \rangle, \quad a_{53} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{53} = \langle b^a_{53}, b^c_{53}, \beta_{53} \rangle, \\ b^a_{53} = R(5, 0, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{53} = \lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, \quad b^c_{53} = \beta_{53}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{63} = \langle a_{63}, b'_{63} \rangle, \quad a_{63} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}6_2]\}, \\ b'_{63} = \langle b^a_{63}, b^c_{63}, \beta_{63} \rangle, \quad b^a_{63} = R(2, 5, x)[+, 6_2] \vee N(x, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{63} = \lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \\ b^c_{63} = \beta_{63}D^c_6 = S(x, 0)[6_2, +]$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\},$$

$$d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, \quad w_1 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], \quad d^*_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_2 = R_2 \div w_2, \quad w_2 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], \quad d^*_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_3 = R_2 \div w_3, \quad w_3 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], \quad d^*_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_4 = R_2 \div w_4, \quad w_4 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +], \quad d^*_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_5 = R_2 \div w_5, \quad w_5 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], \quad d^*_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_6 = R_2 \div w_6, \quad w_6 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +], \quad d^*_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +].$$

$$x = a_{13} \cup a_{23} \cup a_{33} \cup a_{43} \cup a_{53} \cup a_{63} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}6_2],$$

$$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2],$$

$$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}6_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\}$,

$$d_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d_6 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.6.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{7/u, 0/v\}$	$R(7, 0, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{7_2}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{7_2} = \{5/x\}$, $\Delta_{7_2} = \langle a_{7_2}, b'_{7_2} \rangle$, $a_{7_2} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}$, $b'_{7_2} = \langle b^a_{7_2}, b^c_{7_2}, \beta_{7_2} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{7_2} = R(7, 0, 5)[+, 6_2]$, $\beta_{7_2} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{7_2} = \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}$, $b^c_{7_2} = \beta_{7_2} b^c_1 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +]$.

Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$s_1 = \emptyset$.

$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\}$,

$d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}$, $w_{1.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$
 $\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$
 $\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$, $d_{1.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_1 = 2$.

$x_1 = a_{7_2} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_2 = \langle b'_2, d_2, q_2, n_2, s_2, x_2 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_2, d_2]$ и устанавливается $s_2 = \emptyset$, $x_2 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 5/v\}$	$R(0, 5, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{7_2}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{7_2} = \{5/x\}$, $\Delta_{7_2} = \langle a_{7_2}, b'_{7_2} \rangle$, $a_{7_2} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}$, $b'_{7_2} = \langle b^a_{7_2}, b^c_{7_2}, \beta_{7_2} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{7_2} = R(0, 5, 5)[+, 6_2]$, $\beta_{7_2} = \beta_2 \cup \lambda_{7_2} = \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}$, $b^c_{7_2} = \beta_{7_2} b^c_2 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +]$.

Принимается $q_2 = 0$.

$$s_2 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_2 = \{\langle b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{2.1} = d_2 \div w_{2.1}, \quad w_{2.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{2.1} = 0. \text{ Принимается } q_2 = 2.$$

$$x_2 = a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_3 = \langle b'_3, d_3, q_3, n_3, s_3, x_3 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_3, d_3]$ и устанавливается $s_3 = \emptyset, x_3 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{72}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{72} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{72} = \langle a_{72}, b'_{72} \rangle, \quad a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{72} = \langle b^a_{72}, b^c_{72}, \beta_{72} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{72} = R(0, 0, 5)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{72} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{72} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, \quad b^c_{72} = \beta_{72}b^c_3 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{81} = N(5, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_3 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/x\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{91} = N(7, 7)[+, 6_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_3 = S(7, 0)[6_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_3 = 0$.

$$s_3 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_3 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{3.1} = d_3 \div w_{3.1}, \quad w_{3.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +],$$

$$d_{3.1} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.2} = d_3 \div w_{3.2}, \quad w_{3.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +],$$

$$d_{3.2} = N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.3} = d_3 \div w_{3.3}, \quad w_{3.3} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{3.3} = N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]. \\ x_3 = a_{72} \cup a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], \\ R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_4 = \langle b'_4, d_4, q_4, n_4, s_4, x_4 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_4, d_4]$ и устанавливается $s_4 = \emptyset, x_4 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{72}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{72} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{72} = \langle a_{72}, b'_{72} \rangle, \quad a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{72} = \langle b^a_{72}, b^c_{72}, \beta_{72} \rangle, \\ b^a_{72} = R(0, 0, 5)[+, 6_2], \beta_{72} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{72} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, b^c_{72} = \beta_{72}b^c_4 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +]. \\ \lambda_{81} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle, \\ b^a_{81} = N(5, 7)[+, 6_2], \beta_{81} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_4 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +]. \\ \lambda_{91} = \{7/x\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle, \\ b^a_{91} = N(7, 7)[+, 6_2], \beta_{91} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}, b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_4 = S(7, 0)[6_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_4 = 0$.

$$s_4 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_4 = \{\langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.3}, d_{4.3} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{4.1} = d_4 \div w_{4.1}, \quad w_{4.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{4.1} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.2} = d_4 \div w_{4.2}, \quad w_{4.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \\ d_{4.2} = N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.3} = d_4 \div w_{4.3}, \quad w_{4.3} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{4.3} = N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_4 = a_{72} \cup a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], \\ R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_5 = \langle b'_5, d_5, q_5, n_5, s_5, x_5 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_5, d_5]$ и устанавливается $s_5 = \emptyset, x_5 = \emptyset$.

$\{5/u, 0/v\}$	$R(5, 0, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{72}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$\lambda_{72} = \{5/x\}, \quad \Delta_{72} = \langle a_{72}, b'_{72} \rangle, \quad a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{72} = \langle b^a_{72}, b^c_{72}, \beta_{72} \rangle, \\ b^a_{72} = R(5, 0, 5)[+, 6_2], \beta_{72} = \beta_5 \cup \lambda_{72} = \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, b^c_{72} = \beta_{72}b^c_5 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_5 = 0$.

$$s_5 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_5 = \{\langle b'_{5.1}, d_{5.1} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{5.1} = d_5 \div w_{5.1}, \quad w_{5.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], d_{5.1} = 0. \text{ Принимается } q_5 = 2.$$

$$x_5 = a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_6 = \langle b'_6, d_6, q_6, n_6, s_6, x_6 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_6, d_6]$ и устанавливается $s_6 = \emptyset, x_6 = \emptyset$.

$\{2/u, 5/v\}$	$R(2, 5, x)[+, 6_2]$	$N(x, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{72}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{72} = \{5/x\}$, $\Delta_{72} = \langle a_{72}, b'_{72} \rangle$, $a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}$, $b'_{72} = \langle b^a_{72}, b^c_{72}, \beta_{72} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{72} = R(2, 5, 5)[+, 6_2]$, $\beta_{72} = \beta_6 \cup \lambda_{72} = \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}$, $b^c_{72} = \beta_{72}b^c_6 = S(5, 0)[6_2, +]$.

Принимается $q_6 = 0$.

$s_6 = \emptyset$.

$n_6 = \{\langle b'_{6.1}, d_{6.1} \rangle\}$,

$d_{6.1} = d_6 \div w_{6.1}$, $w_{6.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$
 $\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$
 $\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$, $d_{6.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_6 = 2$.

$x_6 = a_{72} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}$.

$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 \cup s_2 \cup s_3 \cup s_4 \cup s_5 \cup s_6 = S_0 = \emptyset$.

$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 \cup x_2 \cup x_3 \cup x_4 \cup x_5 \cup x_6 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}6_2],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}6_2],$
 $N(5, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$
 $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}6_2]\}$.

$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle\}$, т.к. $\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle$, $\langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle$,
 $\langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.3}, d_{4.3} \rangle$.

$h = 1$.

2.1.1.6.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.1} = \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}, q_{3.1}, n_{3.1}, s_{3.1}, x_{3.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.1} = \emptyset$, $x_{3.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}$	$R(0, 0, 5)[+, 6_2]$
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1

$$\lambda_{11} = \emptyset, \quad \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, \quad a_{11} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, \quad b^a_{11} = 0, \\ \beta_{11} = \beta_{3.1} \cup \lambda_{11} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, \quad b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}b^c_{3.1} = S(5, 0)[6_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_{3.1} = 0$.

$$s_{3.1} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +]\}.$$

$$n_{3.1} = \emptyset, \quad q_{3.1} = 1.$$

$$x_{3.1} = a_{11} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.2} = \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}, q_{3.2}, n_{3.2}, s_{3.2}, x_{3.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.2} = \emptyset, x_{3.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}$	$N(5, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1

$$\lambda_{11} = \emptyset, \quad \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, \quad a_{11} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, \quad b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, \quad b^a_{11} = 0, \\ \beta_{11} = \beta_{3.2} \cup \lambda_{11} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}, \quad b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}b^c_{3.2} = S(5, 0)[6_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_{3.2} = 0$.

$$s_{3.2} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +]\}.$$

$$n_{3.2} = \emptyset, \quad q_{3.2} = 1.$$

$$x_{3.2} = a_{11} = \{N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.3} = \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3}, q_{3.3}, n_{3.3}, s_{3.3}, x_{3.3} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.3} = \emptyset, x_{3.3} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 7/x\}$	$N(7, 7)[+, 6_2]$
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1

$$q_{3.3} = 1, \quad n_{3.3} = \{\langle b'_{3.3.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.3.1} = b'_{3.3}\}.$$

$$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{3.1} \cup s_{3.2} \cup s_{3.3} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +]\}.$$

$$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{3.1} \cup x_{3.2} \cup x_{3.3} = X_1.$$

$$n'_2 = \emptyset, \quad S = S_2, \quad X = X_2.$$

$$2.1.1.6.4. \quad Y = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4\}, \quad y_1 = S(5, 0)[\{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(7, 0, 5)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], \\ y_2 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2],$$

$$y_3 = S(5, 0)[\{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(5, 0, 5)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$$

$$y_4 = S(5, 0)[\{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(2, 5, 5)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2].$$

Поскольку $S \neq \emptyset$ и $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0$, $X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}6_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(7, 0, 5)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(5, 0, 5)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(2, 5, 5)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$

2.1.1.6.5. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_6 = Q$, $S_6 = S$, $X_6 = X$, $Y_6 = Y$.

2.1.1.7. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_7 = \langle D'_7, R_2, u_2, Q_7, S_7, X_7, Y_7 \rangle$.

$$D'_7 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2] \vee S(u, v)[+, 7_2], S(7, y)[7_2, +], \emptyset \rangle,$$

$$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

2.1.1.7.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_7, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_7, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset$, $x = \emptyset$.

$\emptyset$	$R(u, v, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$	$S(u, v)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{33}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{43}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{53}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{63}

$$\lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, \quad a_{13} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle, \\ b^a_{13} = R(7, 0, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle, \quad a_{23} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{23} = \langle b^a_{23}, b^c_{23}, \beta_{23} \rangle, \\ b^a_{23} = R(0, 5, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, b^c_{23} = \beta_{23}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{33} = \langle a_{33}, b'_{33} \rangle, \quad a_{33} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{33} = \langle b^a_{33}, b^c_{33}, \beta_{33} \rangle, \\ b^a_{33} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \beta_{33} = \lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{33} = \beta_{33}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{43} = \langle a_{43}, b'_{43} \rangle, \quad a_{43} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{43} = \langle b^a_{43}, b^c_{43}, \beta_{43} \rangle, \\ b^a_{43} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \beta_{43} = \lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{43} = \beta_{43}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{53} = \langle a_{53}, b'_{53} \rangle, \quad a_{53} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{53} = \langle b^a_{53}, b^c_{53}, \beta_{53} \rangle, \\ b^a_{53} = R(5, 0, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \beta_{53} = \lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{53} = \beta_{53}D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{63} = \langle a_{63}, b'_{63} \rangle, \quad a_{63} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}7_2]\},$$

$$b'_{63} = \langle b^a_{63}, b^c_{63}, \beta_{63} \rangle, \quad b^a_{63} = R(2, 5, w)[+, 7_2] \vee R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2], \quad \beta_{63} = \lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\},$$

$$b^c_{63} = \beta_{63} D^c_7 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$$s = \emptyset.$$

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\},$$

$$d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, \quad w_1 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], \quad d^*_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_2 = R_2 \div w_2, \quad w_2 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], \quad d^*_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_3 = R_2 \div w_3, \quad w_3 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], \quad d^*_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_4 = R_2 \div w_4, \quad w_4 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +], \quad d^*_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_5 = R_2 \div w_5, \quad w_5 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], \quad d^*_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_6 = R_2 \div w_6, \quad w_6 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +], \quad d^*_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +].$$

$$x = a_{13} \cup a_{23} \cup a_{33} \cup a_{43} \cup a_{53} \cup a_{63} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}7_2],$$

$$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}7_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2],$$

$$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}7_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}7_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\}$,

$$d_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d_6 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.7.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{7/u, 0/v\}$	$R(7, 0, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_1 = 1, n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{1.1} = b'_1\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_2 = \langle b'_2, d_2, q_2, n_2, s_2, x_2 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_2, d_2]$ и устанавливается $s_2 = \emptyset, x_2 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 5/v\}$	$R(0, 5, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_2 = 1, n_2 = \{\langle b'_{2,1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{2,1} = b'_2\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_3 = \langle b'_3, d_3, q_3, n_3, s_3, x_3 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_3, d_3]$ и устанавливается $s_3 = \emptyset, x_3 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/w\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{81} = R(7, y, 5)[+, 7_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_3 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle,$$

$$b^a_{91} = R(7, y, 7)[+, 7_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_3 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_3 = 0$.

$$s_3 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_3 = \{\langle b'_{3,1}, d_{3,1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3,2}, d_{3,2} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{3,1} = d_3 \div w_{3,1}, \quad w_{3,1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \quad d_{3,2} = R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.2} = d_3 \div w_{3.2}, \quad w_{3.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{3.2} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_3 = a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}7_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}7_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_4 = \langle b'_4, d_4, q_4, n_4, s_4, x_4 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_4, d_4]$ и устанавливается $s_4 = \emptyset, x_4 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/w\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle, \\ b^a_{81} = R(7, y, 5)[+, 7_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_4 = S(7, y)[7_2, +]. \\ \lambda_{91} = \{7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}7_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle, \\ b^a_{91} = R(7, y, 7)[+, 7_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_4 = S(7, y)[7_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_4 = 0$.

$$s_4 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_4 = \{\langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{4.1} = d_4 \div w_{4.1}, \quad w_{4.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \quad d_{4.1} = R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.2} = d_4 \div w_{4.2}, \quad w_{4.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{4.2} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_4 = a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}7_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}7_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_5 = \langle b'_5, d_5, q_5, n_5, s_5, x_5 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_5, d_5]$ и устанавливается $s_5 = \emptyset, x_5 = \emptyset$.

$\{5/u, 0/v\}$	$R(5, 0, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_5 = 1, n_5 = \{\langle b'_{5.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{5.1} = b'_5\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_6 = \langle b'_6, d_6, q_6, n_6, s_6, x_6 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_6, d_6]$ и устанавливается $s_6 = \emptyset, x_6 = \emptyset$.

$\{2/u, 5/v\}$	$R(2, 5, w)[+, 7_2]$	$R(7, y, w)[+, 7_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$q_6 = 1, n_6 = \{\langle b'_{6.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{6.1} = b'_6\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 \cup s_2 \cup s_3 \cup s_4 \cup s_5 \cup s_6 = S_0 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 \cup x_2 \cup x_3 \cup x_4 \cup x_5 \cup x_6 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}7_2],$$

$$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}7_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}7_2],$$

$$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}7_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}7_2],$$

$$R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}7_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}7_2]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle\}, \text{ т.к. } \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle.$$

$$h = 1.$$

2.1.1.7.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.1} = \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}, q_{3.1}, n_{3.1}, s_{3.1}, x_{3.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.1} = \emptyset, x_{3.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}$	$R(7, y, 5)[+, 7_2]$
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1

$q_{3.1} = 1, n_{3.1} = \{\langle b'_{3.1.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.1.1} = b'_{3.1}\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.2} = \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}, q_{3.2}, n_{3.2}, s_{3.2}, x_{3.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.2} = \emptyset, x_{3.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}$	$R(7, y, 7)[+, 7_2]$
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1

$q_{3.2} = 1, n_{3.2} = \{\langle b'_{3.2.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.2.1} = b'_{3.2}\}$.

$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{3.1} \cup s_{3.2} = S_1 = \emptyset$.

$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{3.1} \cup x_{3.2} = X_1$.

$n'_2 = \emptyset, S = S_2, X = X_2$.

2.1.1.7.4. Поскольку $S = \emptyset$ и $Y = \emptyset$, то $Q = 1, X = \emptyset$.

2.1.1.7.5. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_7 = Q, S_7 = S, X_7 = X, Y_7 = Y$.

2.1.1.8. **Выполняется процедура** $\Omega_8 = \langle D'_8, R_2, u_2, Q_8, S_8, X_8, Y_8 \rangle$.

$D'_8 = \langle R(u, v, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2] \vee S(u, v)[+, 8_2], S(x, 5)[8_2, +], \theta \rangle$,

$R_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$.

2.1.1.8.1. Выполняется процедура $\omega = \langle D'_8, R_2, q, n^*, s, x \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[D'_8, R_2]$ и устанавливается $s = \emptyset, x = \emptyset$.

θ	$R(u, v, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$	$S(u, v)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{13}
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{23}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{33}
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{43}
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{53}
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1	Δ_{63}

$\lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, \Delta_{13} = \langle a_{13}, b'_{13} \rangle, a_{13} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2]\}, b'_{13} = \langle b^a_{13}, b^c_{13}, \beta_{13} \rangle,$

$b^a_{13} = R(7, 0, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \beta_{13} = \lambda_{13} = \{7/u, 0/v\}, b^c_{13} = \beta_{13}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +]$.

$\lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, \Delta_{23} = \langle a_{23}, b'_{23} \rangle, a_{23} = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}8_2]\}, b'_{23} = \langle b^a_{23}, b^c_{23}, \beta_{23} \rangle,$

$b^a_{23} = R(0, 5, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \beta_{23} = \lambda_{23} = \{0/u, 5/v\}, b^c_{23} = \beta_{23}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +]$.

$$\lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{33} = \langle a_{33}, b'_{33} \rangle, \quad a_{33} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{33} = \langle b^{a_{33}}, b^{c_{33}}, \beta_{33} \rangle, \\ b^{a_{33}} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \beta_{33} = \lambda_{33} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^{c_{33}} = \beta_{33}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{43} = \langle a_{43}, b'_{43} \rangle, \quad a_{43} = \{S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{43} = \langle b^{a_{43}}, b^{c_{43}}, \beta_{43} \rangle, \\ b^{a_{43}} = R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \beta_{43} = \lambda_{43} = \{0/u, 0/v\}, b^{c_{43}} = \beta_{43}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, \quad \Delta_{53} = \langle a_{53}, b'_{53} \rangle, \quad a_{53} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{53} = \langle b^{a_{53}}, b^{c_{53}}, \beta_{53} \rangle, \\ b^{a_{53}} = R(5, 0, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \beta_{53} = \lambda_{53} = \{5/u, 0/v\}, b^{c_{53}} = \beta_{53}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \quad \Delta_{63} = \langle a_{63}, b'_{63} \rangle, \quad a_{63} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2]\}, \\ b'_{63} = \langle b^{a_{63}}, b^{c_{63}}, \beta_{63} \rangle, \quad b^{a_{63}} = R(2, 5, w)[+, 8_2] \vee R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2], \quad \beta_{63} = \lambda_{63} = \{2/u, 5/v\}, \\ b^{c_{63}} = \beta_{63}D^c_8 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +]$$

Принимается $q = 0$.

$s = \emptyset$.

$$n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\},$$

$$d^*_1 = R_2 \div w_1, \quad w_1 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], \quad d^*_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_2 = R_2 \div w_2, \quad w_2 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], \quad d^*_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_3 = R_2 \div w_3, \quad w_3 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], \quad d^*_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_4 = R_2 \div w_4, \quad w_4 = S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +], \quad d^*_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_5 = R_2 \div w_5, \quad w_5 = S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], \quad d^*_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +].$$

$$d^*_6 = R_2 \div w_6, \quad w_6 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +], \quad d^*_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \\ \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +].$$

$$x = a_{13} \cup a_{23} \cup a_{33} \cup a_{43} \cup a_{53} \cup a_{63} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2], \\ S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], \\ S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2]\}.$$

Поскольку $q \neq 1$, то $n^* = \{\langle b'_1, d^*_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d^*_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d^*_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d^*_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d^*_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d^*_6 \rangle\}$,

$$d_1 = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_2 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_3 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_4 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \\ \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_5 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_6 = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$n'_0 = \{\langle b'_1, d_1 \rangle, \langle b'_2, d_2 \rangle, \langle b'_3, d_3 \rangle, \langle b'_4, d_4 \rangle, \langle b'_5, d_5 \rangle, \langle b'_6, d_6 \rangle\}, h = 0, S_0 = s, X_0 = x.$$

2.1.1.8.2. Выполняется процедура $\omega_1 = \langle b'_1, d_1, q_1, n_1, s_1, x_1 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_1, d_1]$ и устанавливается $s_1 = \emptyset, x_1 = \emptyset$.

$\{7/u, 0/v\}$	$R(7, 0, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle, \quad a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle, \\ b^a_{62} = R(7, 0, 7)[+, 8_2], \beta_{62} = \beta_1 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}, b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_1 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_1 = 0$.

$$s_1 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_1 = \{\langle b'_{1.1}, d_{1.1} \rangle\},$$

$d_{1.1} = d_1 \div w_{1.1}, \quad w_{1.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}]$
 $\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$
 $\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], d_{1.1} = 0.$ Принимается $q_1 = 2.$
 $x_1 = a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_2 = \langle b'_2, d_2, q_2, n_2, s_2, x_2 \rangle.$

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_2, d_2]$ и устанавливается $s_2 = \emptyset, x_2 = \emptyset.$

$\{0/u, 5/v\}$	$R(0, 5, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle, \quad a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle,$
 $b^a_{62} = R(0, 5, 7)[+, 8_2], \beta_{62} = \beta_2 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}, b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_2 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$

Принимается $q_2 = 0.$

$s_2 = \emptyset.$

$n_2 = \{\langle b'_{2.1}, d_{2.1} \rangle\},$

$d_{2.1} = d_2 \div w_{2.1}, \quad w_{2.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_{1, +}] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_{1, +}]$
 $\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_{1, +}] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_{1, +}] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$
 $\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], d_{2.1} = 0.$ Принимается $q_2 = 2.$
 $x_2 = a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_3 = \langle b'_3, d_3, q_3, n_3, s_3, x_3 \rangle.$

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_3, d_3]$ и устанавливается $s_3 = \emptyset, x_3 = \emptyset.$

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle, \quad a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle, \\ b^a_{62} = R(0, 0, 7)[+, 8_2], \beta_{62} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}, b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_3 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/w\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle, \\ b^a_{81} = R(5, x, 5)[+, 8_2], \beta_{81} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}, b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_3 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle, \\ b^a_{91} = R(5, x, 7)[+, 8_2], \beta_{91} = \beta_3 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}, b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_3 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_3 = 0$.

$$s_3 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_3 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{3.1} = d_3 \div w_{3.1}, \quad w_{3.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{3.1} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.2} = d_3 \div w_{3.2}, \quad w_{3.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \\ d_{3.2} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{3.3} = d_3 \div w_{3.3}, \quad w_{3.3} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{3.3} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_3 = a_{62} \cup a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2], \\ R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_4 = \langle b'_4, d_4, q_4, n_4, s_4, x_4 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_4, d_4]$ и устанавливается $s_4 = \emptyset, x_4 = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v\}$	$R(0, 0, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	Δ_{81}	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{91}	1

$$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle, \quad a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle, \\ b^a_{62} = R(0, 0, 7)[+, 8_2], \quad \beta_{62} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}, \quad b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_4 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{81} = \{5/w\}, \quad \Delta_{81} = \langle a_{81}, b'_{81} \rangle, \quad a_{81} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{81} = \langle b^a_{81}, b^c_{81}, \beta_{81} \rangle, \\ b^a_{81} = R(5, x, 5)[+, 8_2], \quad \beta_{81} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{81} = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}, \quad b^c_{81} = \beta_{81}b^c_4 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

$$\lambda_{91} = \{7/w\}, \quad \Delta_{91} = \langle a_{91}, b'_{91} \rangle, \quad a_{91} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{91} = \langle b^a_{91}, b^c_{91}, \beta_{91} \rangle, \\ b^a_{91} = R(5, x, 7)[+, 8_2], \quad \beta_{91} = \beta_4 \cup \lambda_{91} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}, \quad b^c_{91} = \beta_{91}b^c_4 = S(x, 5)[8_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_4 = 0$.

$$s_4 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_4 = \{\langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{4.3}, d_{4.3} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{4.1} = d_4 \div w_{4.1}, \quad w_{4.1} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{4.1} = R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.2} = d_4 \div w_{4.2}, \quad w_{4.2} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +], \\ d_{4.2} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +].$$

$$d_{4.3} = d_4 \div w_{4.3}, \quad w_{4.3} = S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +] \\ \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \\ d_{4.3} = R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +].$$

$$x_4 = a_{62} \cup a_{81} \cup a_{91} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2], \\ R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_5 = \langle b'_5, d_5, q_5, n_5, s_5, x_5 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_5, d_5]$ и устанавливается $s_5 = \emptyset, x_5 = \emptyset$.

$\{5/u, 0/v\}$	$R(5, 0, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}$, $\Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle$, $a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$, $b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{62} = R(5, 0, 7)[+, 8_2]$, $\beta_{62} = \beta_5 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$, $b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_5 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +]$.

Принимается $q_5 = 0$.

$s_5 = \emptyset$.

$n_5 = \{\langle b'_{5.1}, d_{5.1} \rangle\}$,

$d_{5.1} = d_5 \div w_{5.1}$, $w_{5.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$

$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$

$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$, $d_{5.1} = 0$. Принимается $q_5 = 2$.

$x_5 = a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$.

Выполняется процедура $\omega_6 = \langle b'_6, d_6, q_6, n_6, s_6, x_6 \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_6, d_6]$ и устанавливается $s_6 = \emptyset$, $x_6 = \emptyset$.

$\{2/u, 5/v\}$	$R(2, 5, w)[+, 8_2]$	$R(5, x, w)[+, 8_2]$
$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +]$	1	1
$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$	1	1
$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +]$	1	1
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1	Δ_{62}
$N(5, 7)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1	1

$\lambda_{62} = \{2/x, 7/w\}$, $\Delta_{62} = \langle a_{62}, b'_{62} \rangle$, $a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$, $b'_{62} = \langle b^a_{62}, b^c_{62}, \beta_{62} \rangle$,
 $b^a_{62} = R(2, 5, 7)[+, 8_2]$, $\beta_{62} = \beta_6 \cup \lambda_{62} = \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$, $b^c_{62} = \beta_{62}b^c_6 = S(2, 5)[8_2, +]$.

Принимается $q_6 = 0$.

$$s_6 = \emptyset.$$

$$n_6 = \{\langle b'_{6.1}, d_{6.1} \rangle\},$$

$$d_{6.1} = d_6 \div w_{6.1}, \quad w_{6.1} = S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +]$$

$$\vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +] \vee R(5, 2, 7)[u, +] \vee N(5, 7)[u, +]$$

$$\vee R(0, 0, 5)[u, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[u, +], \quad d_{6.1} = 0. \text{ Принимается } q_6 = 2.$$

$$x_6 = a_{62} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

$$S_1 = S_0 \cup s_1 \cup s_2 \cup s_3 \cup s_4 \cup s_5 \cup s_6 = S_0 = \emptyset.$$

$$X_1 = X_0 \cup x_1 \cup x_2 \cup x_3 \cup x_4 \cup x_5 \cup x_6 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2],$$

$$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2],$$

$$S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2],$$

$$R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$$

$$R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$$

$$R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

$$n'_1 = \{\langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle, \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle\}, \quad \text{т.к.} \quad \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.1}, d_{4.1} \rangle, \quad \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.2}, d_{4.2} \rangle,$$

$$\langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3} \rangle = \langle b'_{4.3}, d_{4.3} \rangle.$$

$$h = 1.$$

2.1.1.8.3. Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.1} = \langle b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}, q_{3.1}, n_{3.1}, s_{3.1}, x_{3.1} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.1}, d_{3.1}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.1} = \emptyset, x_{3.1} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$	$R(0, 0, 7)[+, 8_2]$
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{21}

$$\lambda_{21} = \emptyset, \quad \Delta_{21} = \langle a_{21}, b'_{21} \rangle, \quad a_{21} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}, \quad b'_{21} = \langle b^a_{21}, b^c_{21}, \beta_{21} \rangle, \quad b^a_{21} = 0,$$

$$\beta_{21} = \beta_{3.1} \cup \lambda_{21} = \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}, \quad b^c_{21} = \beta_{21} b^c_{3.1} = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_{3.1} = 0$.

$$s_{3.1} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +]\}.$$

$$n_{3.1} = \emptyset, \quad q_{3.1} = 1.$$

$$x_{3.1} = a_{21} = \{R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.2} = \langle b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}, q_{3.2}, n_{3.2}, s_{3.2}, x_{3.2} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.2}, d_{3.2}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.2} = \emptyset, x_{3.2} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}$	$R(5, x, 5)[+, 8_2]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	1
$R(0, 0, 7)[u, +]$	1

$$q_{3.2} = 1, n_{3.2} = \{\langle b'_{3.2.1}, 0 \rangle \mid b'_{3.2.1} = b'_{3.2}\}.$$

Выполняется процедура $\omega_{3.3} = \langle b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3}, q_{3.3}, n_{3.3}, s_{3.3}, x_{3.3} \rangle$.

Вычисляется $\mu[b'_{3.3}, d_{3.3}]$ и устанавливается $s_{3.3} = \emptyset, x_{3.3} = \emptyset$.

$\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}$	$R(5, x, 7)[+, 8_2]$
$R(5, 2, 7)[u, +]$	Δ_{11}
$R(0, 0, 5)[u, +]$	1

$$\lambda_{11} = \{2/x\}, \Delta_{11} = \langle a_{11}, b'_{11} \rangle, a_{11} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2]\}, b'_{11} = \langle b^a_{11}, b^c_{11}, \beta_{11} \rangle, b^a_{11} = 0, \beta_{11} = \beta_{3.3} \cup \lambda_{11} = \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}, b^c_{11} = \beta_{11}b^c_{3.3} = S(2, 5)[8_2, +].$$

Принимается $q_{3.3} = 0$.

$$s_{3.3} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2, +]\}.$$

$$n_{3.3} = \emptyset, q_{3.3} = 1.$$

$$x_{3.3} = a_{11} = \{R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2]\}.$$

$$S_2 = S_1 \cup s_{3.1} \cup s_{3.2} \cup s_{3.3} = \{S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2, +]\}.$$

$$X_2 = X_1 \cup x_{3.1} \cup x_{3.2} \cup x_{3.3} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}.$$

$$n'_2 = \emptyset, S = S_2, X = X_2.$$

$$2.1.1.8.4. Y = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4\}, y_1 = S(2, 5)[\{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee R(7, 0, 7)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], y_2 = S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee R(0, 5, 7)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], y_3 = S(2, 5)[\{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee R(5, 0, 7)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], y_4 = S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2].$$

Поскольку $S \neq \emptyset$ и $Y \neq \emptyset$, то $Q = 0, X = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$

$R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$,
 $R(7, 0, 7)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(0, 5, 7)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(5, 0, 7)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$,
 $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$.

2.1.1.8.5. Фиксация результатов выполнения процедуры: $Q_8 = Q$, $S_8 = S$, $X_8 = X$, $Y_8 = Y$.

2.1.1.9 $Q_1 = 0$ ($S_1 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_2 = 0$ ($S_2 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_3 = 0$ ($S_3 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_4 = 0$ ($S_4 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_5 = 1$ ($Y_5 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_6 = 0$ ($S_6 \neq \emptyset$, $Y_6 \neq \emptyset$), $Q_7 = 1$, $Q_8 = 0$ ($S_8 \neq \emptyset$, $Y_8 \neq \emptyset$). Принимается $p_2 = 0$.

2.1.2 **Формируются множества дедуктивных, абдуктивных следствий и дополнительных фактов.**

$e_2 = \{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}1_2, +],$
 $S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_2, +],$
 $S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}3_2, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}3_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}4_2, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}4_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}4_2, +],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2, +]\}$.

Множества абдуктивных следствий и дополнительных фактов до коррекции n_{max} .

$e'_2 = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2, +], S(0, 7)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +]\}$.

$f_2 = \{N(5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], N(7, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2], R(7, 0, 5)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$
 $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(5, 0, 5)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(2, 5, 5)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2],$
 $R(7, 0, 7)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 5, 7)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 0, 7)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$
 $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$.

После коррекции n_{max} .

$e'_2 = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +]\}$.

$f_2 = \{R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$.

2.1.3 **Формируется множество литералов описания схемы вывода и новый выводимый дизъюнкт.**

$z_2 = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2],$

$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}2_2],$

$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{1_1}, \{7/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_1}, \{0/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_1}, \{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_1}, \{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_1}, \{5/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_{8_1}, \{2/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}],$

$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{1_1}, \{7/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_1}, \{0/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_1}, \{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_1}, \{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_1}, \{5/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_{8_1}, \{2/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}],$

$S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_1}, \{0/u, 5/v\}_{6_2}], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_1}, \{0/u, 0/v\}_{6_2}], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_1}, \{0/u, 0/v\}_{6_2}],$
 $N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}],$
 $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}],$

$S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_1}, \{0/u, 0/v\}_{8_2}], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_1}, \{0/u, 0/v\}_{8_2}], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_{8_1}, \{2/u, 5/v\}_{8_2}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}],$
 $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}]\}.$

$R_3 = S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +] \vee S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{1_2}, +] \vee S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +] \vee S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{1_2}, +] \vee S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{2_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +] \vee S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{2_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}_{8_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}, +].$

2.1.4 Фиксируются результаты выполнения процедуры.

2.2 Формирование семейств следствий, дополнительных фактов, описания схемы вывода и проверка признака.

$s^2 = s^1 \cup \{e_2\} = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{1_1}, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_1}, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_1}, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_1}, +]\},$

$\{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{1_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{1_2}, +],$
 $S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{1_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{2_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +],$
 $S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{2_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{2_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{3_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{3_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_{4_2}, +], S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_{4_2}, +],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}_{8_2}, +]\}.$

$\pi^2 = \pi^1 \cup \{e'_2\} = \{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_1}, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_1}, +]\},$

$\{S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}, +]\}.$

$\varphi^2 = \varphi^1 \cup \{f_2\} = \{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_{6_1}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_1}]\},$

$\{R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_{6_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_{8_2}]\}.$

$\eta^2 = \eta^1 \cup \{z_2\} = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1],$
 $S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1],$
 $S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1],$
 $\{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}2_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}2_2],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}2_2], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}3_2],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_2],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}3_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}3_2],$
 $S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}4_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}4_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}4_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/u, 5/v\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$
 $N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/u, 5/v\}8_2],$
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$
 $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$.

Поскольку $h = H$, то вывод завершается.

2.3 Формирование общих множеств следствий, дополнительных фактов и описания схемы вывода.

$M^E = \{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, +],$
 $S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}1_2, +],$
 $S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}1_2, +], S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_2, +],$
 $S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}2_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}2_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}3_2, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}3_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}3_2, +], S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}4_2, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}4_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}4_2, +], S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}4_2, +],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2, +], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v,$
 $2/x, 7/w\}8_1, +], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +]\}$.

$M^G = \{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2],$
 $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]\}$.

$Z = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}2_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}3_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}4_1],$
 $S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}6_1], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}8_1],$
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}1_2],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_1, \{0/x, 5/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_1, \{0/x, 0/y\}1_2],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_1, \{5/x, 0/y\}1_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_1, \{2/x, 5/y\}1_2],$

$S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_2], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_3], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_3],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_3], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_3], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_3],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_3], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_4],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_4], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_4], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_4],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_4], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_4],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/u, 5/v\}_6], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/u, 0/v\}_6], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/u, 0/v\}_6],$
 $N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_6], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6],$
 $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_6], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/u, 0/v\}_8], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/u, 0/v\}_8],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/u, 5/v\}_8], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8],$
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8].$

$e^+ = \{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_1, +], S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_1, +], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, +], S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_1, +],$
 $S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_1, +], S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_2, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, +],$
 $S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_2, +], S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_2, +], S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_3, +], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_3, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, +], S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_3, +], S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_3, +], S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}_4, +],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}_4, +], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, +], S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}_4, +], S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}_4, +],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, +], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}_8, +], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_6, +],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, +].$

$O = \{S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}_1], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}_3], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/x, 0/y\}_4],$
 $S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}_6], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6], S(0, 0)[n, \{0/u, 0/v\}_8],$
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8].$

$\{S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_2], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_2], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_2],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_2], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_2],$
 $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_2], S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_3],$
 $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_3], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_3], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_3],$
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_3], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_3],$
 $S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_1, \{7/x, 0/y\}_4], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/x, 5/y\}_4], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/x, 0/y\}_4],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/x, 0/y\}_4], S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6, \{5/x, 0/y\}_4], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x,$
 $7/w\}_8, \{2/x, 5/y\}_4], S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_2, \{0/u, 5/v\}_6], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/u, 0/v\}_6],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/u, 0/v\}_6], N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_6], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6],$
 $N(5, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}_6], R(0, 5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}_6], S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_3, \{0/u, 0/v\}_8],$
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}_4, \{0/u, 0/v\}_8], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}_8, \{2/u, 5/v\}_8].$

$R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$, $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$,
 $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2]$,

$\{S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}1_2, +]$, $S(7, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}1_2, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}1_2, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}1_2, +]$,
 $S(7, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}1_2, +]$, $S(7, 5)[\{7/x, 0/y\}2_2, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}2_2, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 0/y\}2_2, +]$,
 $S(5, 5)[\{5/x, 0/y\}2_2, +]$, $S(2, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}2_2, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}3_2, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\{0/x, 5/y\}3_2, +]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}3_2, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}3_2, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\{2/x, 5/y\}3_2, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\{7/x, 0/y\}4_2, +]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 5/y\}4_2, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\{0/x, 0/y\}4_2, +]$, $S(5, 0)[\{5/x, 0/y\}4_2, +]$, $S(2, 0)[\{2/x, 5/y\}4_2, +]$,
 $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +]$, $S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/w, 2/x\}8_2, +]$, $S(5, 0)[\{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +]$,
 $S(2, 5)[\{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +]\}$.

Перед построением схемы вывода с целью сокращения числа символов в параметрах литералов вводятся обозначения подстановок, используемых в литералах семейства множеств O : $\lambda_1 = \{0/x, 0/y\}$,
 $\lambda_2 = \{0/u, 0/v\}$, $\lambda_3 = \{0/u, 0/v, 5/x\}$, $\lambda_4 = \{0/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$, $\lambda_5 = \{7/x, 0/y\}$, $\lambda_6 = \{0/x, 5/y\}$, $\lambda_7 = \{5/x, 0/y\}$,
 $\lambda_8 = \{2/x, 5/y\}$, $\lambda_9 = \{0/u, 5/v\}$, $\lambda_{10} = \{0/u, 5/v, 5/x\}$, $\lambda_{11} = \{2/u, 5/v\}$, $\lambda_{12} = \{2/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}$ при этом
 $\lambda_2 \subseteq \lambda_3$, $\lambda_2 \subseteq \lambda_4$, $\lambda_9 \subseteq \lambda_{10}$, $\lambda_{11} \subseteq \lambda_{12}$.

$O = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{111}]$, $S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{121}]$, $S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{131}]$, $S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{141}]$, $S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{261}]$, $N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{361}]$,
 $R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{361}]$, $S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{281}]$, $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{481}]$, $R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{481}]\}$,

$\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{512}]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{612}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{112}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{112}]$, $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{712}]$,
 $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{812}]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{522}]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{622}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{122}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{122}]$,
 $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{722}]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{822}]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{532}]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{632}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{132}]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{132}]$, $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{732}]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{832}]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{542}]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{642}]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{142}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{142}]$, $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{742}]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{842}]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{962}]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{262}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{262}]$, $N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{1062}]$, $R(0, 0, 5)[u, \lambda_{362}]$, $N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{362}]$,
 $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{1062}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{282}]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{282}]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{1182}]$, $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{482}]$,
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{1282}]$, $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \lambda_{482}]$, $R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{1282}]\}$,

$\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{512}, +]$, $S(7, 5)[\lambda_{612}, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{112}, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{712}, +]$, $S(7, 5)[\lambda_{812}, +]$, $S(7, 5)[\lambda_{522}, +]$,
 $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{622}, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{122}, +]$, $S(5, 5)[\lambda_{722}, +]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{822}, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{532}, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{632}, +]$,
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{132}, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{732}, +]$, $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{832}, +]$, $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{542}, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{642}, +]$, $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{142}, +]$,
 $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{742}, +]$, $S(2, 0)[\lambda_{842}, +]$, $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{362}, +]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{482}, +]$, $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{1062}, +]$, $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{1282}, +]\}$.

Схема логического вывода следствий, построенная по описанию O , представлена на рисунке 1. Результаты выполнения процедур вывода представлены в таблице 2.

Рисунок 2 – Схема логического вывода следствий

Таблица 2 – Результаты выполнения процедур вывода

Процедура вывода $\psi_1 (R_1 = S(0, 0)[n, +], p_1 = 0, h = 1)$	
D'_1	$Q_1 = 0, S_1 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11}, +]\}, Y_1 = \emptyset, X_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{11}]\}$
D'_2	$Q_2 = 0, S_2 = \{S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12}, +]\}, Y_2 = \emptyset, X_2 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{12}]\}$
D'_3	$Q_3 = 0, S_3 = \{S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13}, +]\}, Y_3 = \emptyset, X_3 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{13}]\}$
D'_4	$Q_4 = 0, S_4 = \{S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14}, +]\}, Y_4 = \emptyset, X_4 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{14}]\}$
D'_5	$Q_5 = 1, S_5 = \emptyset, Y_5 = \emptyset, X_5 = \emptyset$
D'_6	$Q_6 = 0, S_6 = \emptyset, Y_6 = \{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36}, +] \vee R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}]\}, X_6 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{26}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36}], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}]\}$
D'_7	$Q_7 = 1, S_7 = \emptyset, Y_7 = \emptyset, X_7 = \emptyset$
D'_8	$Q_8 = 0, S_8 = \emptyset, Y_8 = \{S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48}, +] \vee R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\}, X_8 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{28}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\}$
$e_1 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14}, +]\},$ $e'_1 = \{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48}, +]\},$ $f_1 = \{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\},$ $z_1 = \{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{11}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{12}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{13}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{14}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{26}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36}], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{28}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\}$	
$s^1 = \{\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14}, +]\}\},$ $\pi^1 = \{\{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48}, +]\}\},$ $\varphi^1 = \{\{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\}\},$ $\eta^1 = \{\{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{11}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{12}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{13}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{14}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{26}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36}], R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{28}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48}]\}\}$	

Процедура вывода ψ_2 ($R_2 = S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, +]$, $p_2 = 0$, $h = 2$)	
D'_1	$Q_1 = 0, S_1 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{512}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{612}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{112}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{712}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{812}, +]\},$ $Y_1 = \emptyset, X_1 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{512}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{612}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{112}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{112}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{712}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{812}]\}.$
D'_2	$Q_2 = 0, S_2 = \{S(7, 5)[\lambda_{522}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{622}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{122}, +], S(5, 5)[\lambda_{722}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{822}, +]\},$ $Y_2 = \emptyset, X_2 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{522}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{622}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{122}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{122}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{722}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{822}]\}.$
D'_3	$Q_3 = 0, S_3 = \{S(0, 0)[\lambda_{532}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{632}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{132}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{732}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{832}, +]\},$ $Y_3 = \emptyset, X_3 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{532}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{632}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{132}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{132}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{732}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{832}]\}.$
D'_4	$Q_4 = 0, S_4 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{542}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{642}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{142}, +], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{742}, +], S(2, 0)[\lambda_{842}, +]\},$ $Y_4 = \emptyset, X_4 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \lambda_{542}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{642}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{142}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{142}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \lambda_{742}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{842}]\}.$
D'_5	$Q_5 = 0, S_5 = \emptyset, Y_5 = \{S(0, 5)[\{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2, +] \vee N(5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2],$ $S(0, 7)[\{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2, +] \vee N(7, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}, X_5 = \{S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{252}],$ $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{252}], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2],$ $N(5, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 5/y\}5_2], N(7, 5)[+, \{0/u, 0/v, 7/y\}5_2]\}.$
D'_6	$Q_6 = 0, S_6 = \{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{362}, +]\}, Y_6 = \{S(5, 0)[\{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(7, 0, 5)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{1062}, +] \vee R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{1062}], S(5, 0)[\{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(5, 0, 5)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$ $S(5, 0)[\{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2, +] \vee R(2, 5, 5)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}, X_6 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \{7/u, 0/v\}6_2],$ $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{962}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{262}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{262}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \{5/u, 0/v\}6_2],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{1162}], N(5, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{1062}], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \lambda_{362}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{362}],$ $N(5, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], N(5, 7)[u, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(7, 0, 5)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2],$ $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{1062}], R(5, 0, 5)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 5/x\}6_2], R(2, 5, 5)[+, \{2/u, 5/v, 5/x\}6_2]\}.$
D'_7	$Q_7 = 1, S_7 = \emptyset, Y_7 = \emptyset, X_7 = \emptyset$
D'_8	$Q_8 = 0, S_8 = \{S(2, 5)[\lambda_{482}, +]\}, Y_8 = \{S(2, 5)[\{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee$ $R(7, 0, 7)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee$ $R(0, 5, 7)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2, +] \vee$ $R(5, 0, 7)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{1282}, +] \vee R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{1282}]\},$ $X_8 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{111}, \{7/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{121}, \lambda_{982}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{131}, \lambda_{282}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{141}, \lambda_{282}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{361}, \{5/u, 0/v\}8_2], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{481}, \lambda_{1182}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$ $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{482}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$ $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{1282}], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \lambda_{482}], R(7, 0, 7)[+, \{7/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2],$

$R(0, 5, 7)[+, \{0/u, 5/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(5, 0, 7)[+, \{5/u, 0/v, 2/x, 7/w\}8_2], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{12}8_2]$
$e_2 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{51_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{61_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{71_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{81_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{52_2}, +],$ $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{62_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_2}, +], S(5, 5)[\lambda_{72_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{82_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{53_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{63_2}, +],$ $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{73_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{83_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{54_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{64_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_2}, +],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{74_2}, +], S(2, 0)[\lambda_{84_2}, +], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_2}, +]\},$ $e'_2 = \{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{106_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{128_2}, +]\},$ $f_2 = \{R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{106_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{128_2}]\},$ $z_2 = \{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{51_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{61_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{11_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{11_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{71_2}],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{81_2}],$ $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{52_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{62_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{12_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{12_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{72_2}],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{82_2}],$ $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{53_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{63_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{13_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{13_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{73_2}],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{83_2}],$ $S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{54_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{64_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{14_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{14_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{74_2}],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{84_2}],$ $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{96_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{26_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{26_2}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{106_2}], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \lambda_{36_2}],$ $N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36_2}], R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{106_2}],$ $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{28_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{28_2}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{118_2}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48_2}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{128_2}],$ $R(0, 0, 7)[u, \lambda_{48_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{128_2}]\}$
$s^2 = \{\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, +]\},$ $\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{51_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{61_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{71_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{81_2}, +], S(7, 5)[\lambda_{52_2}, +],$ $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{62_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_2}, +], S(5, 5)[\lambda_{72_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{82_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{53_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{63_2}, +],$ $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{73_2}, +], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{83_2}, +], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{54_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{64_2}, +], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_2}, +],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{74_2}, +], S(2, 0)[\lambda_{84_2}, +], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_2}, +]\}\},$ $\pi^2 = \{\{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, +]\},$ $\{S(5, 0)[\lambda_{106_2}, +], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{128_2}, +]\}\},$ $\varphi^2 = \{\{R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36_1}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48_1}]\},$ $\{R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{106_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{128_2}]\}\},$ $\eta^2 = \{\{S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{11_1}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{12_1}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{13_1}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{14_1}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{26_1}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36_1}],$ $R(0, 0, 5)[+, \lambda_{36_1}], S(0, 0)[n, \lambda_{28_1}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48_1}], R(0, 0, 7)[+, \lambda_{48_1}]\},$ $\{S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{51_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{61_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{11_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{11_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{71_2}],$ $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{81_2}], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{52_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{62_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{12_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{12_2}],$ $S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{72_2}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{82_2}], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{13_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{63_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{13_2}],$ $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{13_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{73_2}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{83_2}], S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_1}, \lambda_{54_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{64_2}],$

$S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{14_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{14_2}], S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_1}, \lambda_{74_2}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{84_2}], S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_1}, \lambda_{96_2}],$
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{26_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{26_2}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{106_2}], R(0, 0, 5)[u, \lambda_{36_2}], N(5, 7)[u, \lambda_{36_2}],$
 $R(0, 5, 5)[+, \lambda_{106_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_1}, \lambda_{28_2}], S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_1}, \lambda_{28_2}], S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_1}, \lambda_{118_2}], R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{48_2}],$
 $R(5, 2, 7)[u, \lambda_{128_2}], R(0, 0, 7)[u, \lambda_{48_2}], R(2, 5, 7)[+, \lambda_{128_2}]]$

$h = H = 2, R_3 = S(7, 0)[\lambda_{51_2}, +] \vee S(7, 5)[\lambda_{61_2}, +] \vee S(7, 0)[\lambda_{11_2}, +] \vee S(7, 0)[\lambda_{71_2}, +] \vee S(7, 5)[\lambda_{81_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(7, 5)[\lambda_{52_2}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\lambda_{62_2}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\lambda_{12_2}, +] \vee S(5, 5)[\lambda_{72_2}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\lambda_{82_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{53_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(0, 5)[\lambda_{63_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{13_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{73_2}, +] \vee S(0, 5)[\lambda_{83_2}, +] \vee S(7, 0)[\lambda_{54_2}, +] \vee S(0, 0)[\lambda_{64_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(0, 0)[\lambda_{14_2}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\lambda_{74_2}, +] \vee S(2, 0)[\lambda_{84_2}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\lambda_{36_2}, +] \vee S(2, 5)[\lambda_{48_2}, +] \vee S(5, 0)[\lambda_{106_2}, +] \vee$
 $S(2, 5)[\lambda_{128_2}, +]$